

**IMPACT OF ELECTRICITY POWER SUPPLY ON INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTIVITY
IN NIGERIA (1990 – 2022)**

BY

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JUNE, 2025

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**BEING A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED FOR EXTERNAL DEFENCE TO THE
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JUNE, 2025

DECLARATION

I, **NWANKWO, Glory Ebube**, with Registration number **20/409ECN/065**, hereby declare that this dissertation is strictly my research efforts and contributions to knowledge. Materials for this work were sourced from diverse sources online and offline, and appropriate citations were made. To the best of my knowledge, this entire work was written by me and has never been presented in any academic environment for the purpose of awarding a degree. I take responsibility for all the omissions and errors that might be found in the work.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this dissertation titled “**Impact of Electricity Generation On Industrial Productivity in Nigeria (1990-2022)**” written by **Nwankwo, Glory Ebube**, with registration number **20/409ECN/065** in the department of Economics, Faculty of Social Science, meets the requirement for the award of Master of Science (M.Sc) Economics degree of University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to Almighty God, the author and finisher of our faith, who has made it possible for me to achieve this height, and to my loving mother Mrs. Benedeth Nwankwo who sacrificed materially for my success in school as an undergraduate, laying the foundation for my quest to pursue a Master's Degree, and also to my dearest Uncle Igwe Humphrey Oluna Ejesieme for his fatherly assistance in commencing the Masters program.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of Electricity Supply on Nigeria's Industrial Productivity. The research data was sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) for the period from 1990 to 2022. Two models were estimated; the first evaluated the impact of installed capacity (INCA) and government expenditure on electricity infrastructures (GEXP) on electricity supply, while the second looked into the effect of electricity supply (ELEC) on industrial productivity index (IND), the dependent variable. The neo-classical theory of growth informed the research model, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and trend analysis. Further, OLS estimation was used for the first model to examine the impact of INCA and ELEC on IND. Then, the Johansen cointegration test and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) were employed to understand both long-run and short-run dynamics in the second model of the relationship between ELEC and IND. The findings reveal a significant positive impact of installed capacity on electricity supply. At the same time, ELEC (0.6913) had a long-run positive impact on industrial productivity. However, government expenditure on electricity infrastructure positive impact on ELEC, was statistically insignificant. Four hypotheses were tested, and three were rejected due to the findings of no statistical evidence. Based on these findings, the study recommends strategic capital budgeting concerning power infrastructures, enhancing installed capacity, and promoting renewable energy sources to increase the power supply. Strengthening grid reliability and ensuring effective policy coordination were also recommended to sustain industrial productivity growth through improved electricity supply.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Electricity is a major component of a country's national sector, and a key source for advancement and improvement in people's standard of living by stimulating the industrial sectors in the economy (Ariyo, 2023). According to Jack (2022) and Ariyo (2023), energy is a crucial component of production for businesses, and its scarcity might limit productivity because it is not as sustainable as other production components. Furthermore, the government used electricity to provide vital services to the public, which include healthcare and schooling. Moreover, using electricity might boost the well-being of households and produce efficiency advantages like time savings, better interaction, and investments in education. It is also important to note that energy infrastructure requires other types of complementary infrastructure to assist overall economic growth (Jack, 2022; Ariyo, 2023).

From the foregoing, Electricity has been depicted to be essential for all aspects of modern life, from powering our homes and industries to manufacturing goods and providing transportation. Thus, an efficient generation and utilisation of power brings about an increase in industrial productivity, which in turn speeds up economic growth and development (Oyedepo, 2012). Industrial productivity here measures how much output is produced by a given amount of input, such as energy, labour, and capital. Since a healthy manufacturing sector is essential for an economy to experience sustainable growth, a vibrant manufacturing sector provides the necessary

impetus for quick and favourable economic expansion. Therefore, Electricity is seen as the main component that promotes the efficiency and productivity of other factors of production, particularly labour and capital, in a modern economy where industrialisation is gaining momentum and mass production is needed for local consumption and exports (Udah, 2010).

Over the years, the Nigerian power generation industry is faced with certain issues owing to infrastructure constraints together with the stages of the value chain from power to its distribution, including fixed sources of energy for electricity (80% thermal and 20% hydro), insufficient gas pipelines, outdated generation facilities and equipment, along with pitifully and inefficiently maintained channels of distribution as well as transmission (Ariyo, 2023). Going forward, this has caused the Nation to constantly operate on a Generator economy, which has adversely affected its industrial sector's production cost. There have also been frequent power shortages in the nation, despite having abundant access to a variety of energy resources, including crude oil, natural gas, coal, hydropower, solar energy, and fissionable materials for nuclear energy, which is a significant barrier to country's ability to advance industrially and technologically (Quadri and Bukola, 2022).

However, Nigeria has, over the last 50 years, upheld the hope of transforming her economy through the pursuit of industrialization, to enable her to be more export-oriented and dynamic in nature, exporting industrial goods, as opposed to being import-dependent, inefficient and monolithic (Akinbola, 2018). For this reason, successive Federal Governments have embodied these pursuits in their development plans, especially the first and second development plans of the nation, which were reinforced further by the windfall gains from the crude oil boom of the years 1972/73 and 1979/80 (Akinbola, 2018). Although subsequent administrations have come and gone, implementing a range of deregulation programs that are supposed to aid and speed up the process

of industrialization in the country and create a more favourable environment for manufacturing, the industrial sector has not improved (Adeoye, 2004). The extent of this is highlighted by the fact that Nigeria is the largest purchaser of standby electricity-generating plants in the world (Braithwaite and Okeke 2010).

According to Udah (2010), industrialization is the planned and continuous integration of relevant technology, infrastructure, managerial experts, and other significant resources. The author went on to remark that because of industrialization's critical function in economic development and how fundamental it has become to the economy of every nation; Development Economists have taken a keen interest in the contemporary. For starters, research has shown that industrialization is significantly responsible for the growth and economic development of a country. This explains why industrialization has continually been highlighted as a strategy for transforming the economy of developing governments like Nigeria (Nwankwo & Njogo, 2013).

During the Fourth National Development Plan, which ran from 1981 to 1985, there was a 10% increase in power consumption growth rate which was caused by the oil boom. The existing capacity struggled to meet demand from both residential and industrial consumers due to a strong rate of development (Quadri and Bukola, 2022). There was a record of poor performance in about two decades after the independence of the manufacturing sector, especially in the areas of production and international trade, as the sector remained dependent heavily on imported goods and was vulnerable to external shocks. However, there were also good reports following the establishment of industries such as steel, Textiles, Cement, etc. (Akinbola, 2018).

Since 1999, Numerous power plants have been built by democratically elected governments in Nigeria, such as the Egbin Power Station, the Omoku Power Plants, Kainji Hydro Power Plant, the Jebba Hydro Power Station, etc. But the country's economy has not yet reaped the full benefits of these huge expenditures. According to Ogundipe and Ayomide (2013), the majority of cottage businesses created to promote local content have been effectively eliminated as a result of the high cost of energy production, as these sectors require the operation of independent power plants in order to operate at their peak efficiency. There has also been a lot of development undergone during this period, such as road plans created for the power industry to boost the manufacturing sector and diversify the economy through local content (Olufemi 2015).

Nigeria saw shifts from the government actively participating in electricity generation to several private sector efforts being encouraged to participate in power generation as early as the beginning of the twenty-first century. To improve power generation, distribution, and satisfy the consumption needs of homes and the manufacturing sector, more hydroelectric facilities were also built and put into operation including the Kainji Dam in Niger State commissioned in 1968, also we have the Ikere Gorge Dam located at Oyo state etc. (Salau, 2011). However, as her population swelled significantly, the need for power grew as well, necessitating a massive energy supply to maintain sustainability (Okungbowa and Abhulimen, 2021). This overdependence constantly puts the country in an energy consumption crisis when these resources are not readily available. NERC reports that due to issues with the supply of gas, transmission and distribution limitations, and commercial difficulties, only 53% of the total (electricity) capacity is being used. As a result, families and businesses across Nigeria are receiving subpar power supplies.

In an effort to improve efficiency in electricity power supply, the Nigerian government began investigating reforms to the power sector in 2003. One of the factors that contributed to this was an increase in industrial productivity. The Electric Power Sector Reform (EPSR) Act was approved by the Nigerian government in 2005. According to Adoghe, Odigwe, and Igbinovia (2009), the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) was split into 18 distinct businesses after this Act was passed. These corporations included the Transmission Business of Nigeria (TCN), a transmission company, and six generation companies (GenCos). In order to regulate the sector, the EPSR Act also gave rise to the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC). This was eventually replaced by the power sector's privatisation, which began in 2013; TCN, however, was still held by the government. However, private investors purchased the DisCos and GenCos. in 2020 (Idowu, Ibietan, and Olukotun).

The following are some of the ways that privatising the power sector was suggested to boost industrial productivity. Private investors were always expected to provide the money and knowledge needed to make investments in new technical infrastructures that will increase the industry's productivity. Additionally, it was hoped that competition between a number of DisCos and GenCos would guarantee higher service quality at reduced costs for consumers. But the privatisation process has been arduous and dragged out. There have been several glitches and delays, and some of the private investors have had issues keeping to their contractual obligations. As a result, the power industry still faces a variety of difficulties, such as poor infrastructure, fraud, power instability, and expensive rates (PwC, 2020).

As a substitute, solar energy and other energy sources that generate either entirely or in part from the sun's beam energy are now being used more frequently (Agbo, Edet, Magu, Njok Ekpo, and

Louis, 2022). However, according to Abdullahi, Suresh, Renukappa, and Oloke (2017), solar power technologies have also been impeded by several barriers, such as the high upfront costs required. These difficulties have slowed down the development of solar installations in Nigeria, making their completion all but impossible. These have also led to the development of obstacles that have had a negative impact on the state's power sector, halting the production capacity of several manufacturing firms. In addition, the nation has seen a sizable number of Nigerians relocate their businesses to nearby nations like Ghana and the Republic of Benin because of the unstable power supply. Agbo, Edet, Magu, Njok Ekpo, and Louis, 2022).

On June 9, 2023, President Bola Tinubu formally signed the Electricity Act of 2023. This repeal of the Electric Power Industry Reform Act of 2005 (EPSRA) intends to harmonise Nigeria's electrical regulations along the whole value chain of the country's power industry, including the incorporation of renewable energy sources into Nigeria's energy mix. The Act aims to increase both private-sector investment and state government involvement in the nation's power sector (Adebowale & Makinde, 2023). Therefore, the Federal Government no longer mandates that people or states apply for a license in order to generate, transfer, and distribute electricity (Izuaka, 2023).

One of the major changes brought about by the Power Act of 2023 is the de-monopolization of the national power market. As a result, the federal government no longer requires individuals, businesses, or states to obtain the relevant licenses, making the electrical sector more open to competition and investment. Thereafter, it is hoped that this new development will result in lower electricity prices and greater service quality for both consumers and companies (Izuaka, 2023).. Therefore, it can be argued that several positive effects on industrial productivity are anticipated

as a result of these changes. However, a reliable, cost-effective supply of electricity is necessary for businesses to operate efficiently and successfully. Therefore, the expectation is that this new Electricity Act 2023 will improve the supply and affordability of electricity in Nigeria, boosting industrial productivity. (Izuaka, 2023).

The Electricity Act of 2023 is expected to promote the growth of renewable energy in Nigeria. This is because renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, are sustainable and clean (Aduloju, 2023). By reducing Nigeria's reliance on imported fossil fuels, renewable energy can also help boost the Nigerian economy by creating new jobs and investment opportunities, which in turn can lead to increased industrial productivity. In conclusion, the 2023 Energy Act is an essential piece of legislation that most likely will favourably impact Nigeria's energy industry and industrial productivity in several ways (Aduloju, 2023).

Based on this background, the aim of this study is to ascertain whether the availability of power for industries in Nigeria has a significant influence on their capacity to produce and meet the demands of the nation. This is accomplished by attempting to fill a critical gap in the bulk of scientific studies on the relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity by examining the long- and short-run interactions that may exist between these variables of interest.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is no news that Nigeria has a reputation for having an epileptic power supply. Certain populations lack access to this fundamental social infrastructure, and those who do cannot rely on the historically subpar supply from the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) tends to deploy alternative measures which involve great cost (Nwankwo and Njogo, 2013). As previously

highlighted, Nigeria has also been frequent power shortages in the nation, despite having abundant access to a variety of energy resources, including crude oil, natural gas, coal, hydropower, solar energy, and fissionable materials for nuclear energy, which is a significant barrier to country's ability to advance industrially and technologically (Quadri and Bukola, 2022). According to the World Bank, epileptic power supply costs businesses in Nigeria about \$29 billion yearly (Udegbonam, 2021). Sequel to this, the country's industrialization has suffered, despite the conscious attempts of various government administrations to increase the availability of electricity by passing laws to regulate the industry. The Tinubu administration has made similar attempts to increase power production by enacting another electricity act on June 9, 2023, to support the production of power from renewable power sources. Accordingly, the Electric Power Sector Reform Act of 2005 (EPSRA) was repealed (Adebowale, Makinde, 2023). Calling for increased funding for research and development of renewable power solutions, which stands as a global issue (Onojason, Ole, and Ezike, 2023).

The problem of industries and residential houses having to bear the cost of buying generating units to power their buildings to meet demands still lingers; all resulting from the several electrical shortages the nation has faced. For instance, its electricity grid crashed thrice in a single week in 2022 alone. Additionally, the "Nigeria's State of Power: Electrifying the Nation's Economy" report of 2022 informs us that the excessive sum paid by these households to fuel their generators had a negative impact on their expenses and hampered the expansion of their businesses. Unquestionably, the country's epileptic electrical supply has hampered the nation's economic progress. Both large and small firms have a heavy reliance on self-generated power, which limits their ability to remain competitive, hence being forced to relocate or close their doors (Nwankwo

and Njogo, 2013). Nigeria should therefore take into account how the generation of electricity will evolve, leveraging power from renewable sources like wind and solar power which continues to be one of the most rapidly expanding ways to obtain greener, cleaner electricity. It also indicates that more areas of our lives that presently use fossil fuels will need to switch to using electricity in order to cut carbon emissions and attain net zero. (Ariyo, 2023). In light of the foregoing, we see a number of studies have explored the impact of electricity generation on Nigeria's industrial productivity such as Abraham (2015) and Olayemi (2012) who both both found a positive correlation, with Abraham emphasising the need for prudent use of funds and deregulation of the power sector and Olayemi suggesting the initiation of independent power projects. However, Nwajinka (2013) and Elekwa (2016) presented contrasting views, with Nwajinka finding no significant impact and Elekwa identifying a negative impact. These studies collectively highlight the complex and multifaceted nature of the relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity in Nigeria. It is, therefore, on this basis that this present study gave attention to this issue to contribute to the discourse regarding the productivity of industries in Nigeria.

1.3. Research Questions

Based on the problems discussed above, the study seeks to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the impact of electricity supply on Nigeria's industrial productivity?
- ii. Does a long-run relationship exist between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria?
- iii. How does capacity utilization affect Nigeria's electricity supply?

- iv. What is the impact of government expenditure on power generation on electricity supply?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research study is to examine the impact of Electricity Generation on Industrial Productivity in Nigeria. To achieve this objective, the study will consider the following specific objectives:

- i. To examine the impact of electricity supply on industrial productivity in Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the long-run relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria.
- iii. To determine the effect of Capacity utilisation on electricity supply in Nigeria.
- iv. To ascertain the impact of government expenditure on power on electricity supply.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The research's hypotheses are presented below in their null form (Ho), based on the objectives listed above:

H1: Electricity supply has no significant impact on industrial productivity in Nigeria.

H2: There is no significant long-run relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria.

H3: Capacity utilization does not significantly affect electricity supply in Nigeria

H4: Government expenditure on power has no significant impact on electricity supply

1.6. Significance of the Study

The epileptic electricity supply and its impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria have attracted considerable research, albeit with different conclusions. Some studies have shown that the relationship is positive and significant (Akinbola, Zekeri, and Idowu, 2017; Ekene and Mboho, 2019; Ibrahim, Mukhtar, and Gani, 2017; Onwe and King, 2020; Ugwoke, Dike, and Elekwa, 2016) some revealed that it is positive and insignificant (Agbede and Onuoha, 2020; Chinedum and Nnadi, 2016; Kassim and Isik, 2020) and others showed that the relationship is negative (Asaleye, Lawal, Inegbedion, and Omowumi, 2021; Lawal and Owoicho, 2021). Without a doubt, the study of energy generation and industrial productivity is, therefore, a critical field that is essential for understanding the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century.

There are several opportunities and challenges that need to be handled as the fields of producing electricity and industrial productivity are continually changing. In order to secure a sustainable and prosperous future for the Nigerian economy, it is therefore imperative that continuing studies be conducted, given its continually shifting nature. In light of this, this study investigates how Nigeria's industrial productivity is affected by power supply in an effort to add to the myriad of discussions already in existence, with an emphasis on how the country's issue with industrial productivity is brought on by a lack of electricity supply, capacity factor, and government spending on electricity to spur industrial growth.

Furthermore, this research will also serve as pragmatic knowledge and enlighten the government to devise, modify and adopt a better electricity policy to boost industrialization and also to improve as well as the welfare of the citizenry of Nigeria. In addition, leveraging electricity from renewable

sources like wind and solar power, which continues to be one of the most rapid, would allow the nation to expand its power supply to obtain greener, cleaner electricity.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study investigated the impact of power generation on industrial productivity in Nigeria. To fully capture its effect on the economy, a thorough empirical investigation was carried out using data spanning 32 years, from 1990 to 2022, during which consistent data for the research variables were available.

1.8 Structure of the Study

This study is divided into five chapters. Chapter 1 contains the general introduction, which provides the background to the study, a statement of the problem, objectives of the study, research questions, research hypotheses, significance of the study, scope of the study, and study structure.

Chapter two discusses the key concepts of the research, then the next sub-section provides a theoretical background and a summary of the empirical literature, examining the works of other researchers on the subject matter of electricity generation and industrial productivity. After that, identified gaps in the literature are discussed, and a theoretical framework is presented.

Going forward, Chapter 3 labels the propose methodology of the study to be employed. Specifically, the chapter consist of the research design, model specification, variables measurement, nature and sources of data, and lastly, estimation and evaluation of research techniques and procedure.

Chapter four focuses on the presentation and interpretation of results, such as descriptive analysis of the research data, unit root test, trend analysis, empirical analysis of the model estimated in chapter three, interpretation and discussion of the research findings, and further implications for policy, social, or organizational change, as the case may be.

Finally, section five draws conclusions based on the results and highlights possible recommendations, stating the contribution to knowledge and suggesting future studies.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

2.1.1. The Concept of Electricity Generation

Electricity energy is a secondary form of energy and as such cannot be directly obtained in nature, rather it is usually converted from other forms of energy such as fossil fuels (coal, natural gas, and petroleum), renewable energy (wind, solar, geothermal) sources and nuclear power (bio-fuels, biomass and un-identified data). Then, this energy source is used to create heat or another energy form, which is then converted into mechanical energy to do work (Atomberg, 2016). The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), (2023) defined electricity generation as “the electricity generated from Fossil fuels, nuclear power plants, hydro-power plants (excluding pumped storage), geothermal systems, solar panels, bio-fuels, wind, etc.” Further, they describe it as the power obtained from electricity-only plants and power and heat plants combined. According to the United States Energy Information Administration’s (EIA) electric power monthly data, Fossil fuels are the largest sources of energy for electricity as the survey showed that about 40% of the electricity generation in 2022 was from natural gas.

According to Naheeda, (2022), the fundamental principle behind the concept of electricity generation can be traced back to the 1820s and early 1830s, attributing that it was by Michael Faraday, a British Scientist whose methods of generating electricity form the basis used by most of the world in generating electricity till this contemporary times. Specifically in 1931, Michael

Faraday generated current by moving a magnet inside a coil of wires, hence resulting in the first electricity generator called Faraday disk. A plethora number of studies have it that this is the most common method of electricity generation. Since 1881, electricity has been produced industrially by mankind. Hydroelectric and coal power were utilised in the early power plants (Hassan, 2014). However, there are several other generators, working in the same manner. The different types of generators only differ on the ground of their primary energy source. An Electric generator is any device that can convert a form of energy into electricity (Slemon, 2023).

Power plants are facilities employed where electricity is generated, and the technological requirement of the power plant type depends on the source of energy to be used for conversion. However common types are coal-fired power plants, natural gas power plants, nuclear power plants, solar farms, wind farms, and hydroelectric dams. Now, irrespective of the source of energy to be used, the conversion process of one energy form to generating electricity is somewhat the same. The popular processes involved in converting energy are:

- i. **Heat Generation:** Heat is produced by energy sources, either via nuclear reactions, combustion, or other processes.
- ii. **Steam Production:** This is another basic step in energy conversion. When heat is generated, it is used to boil water and create high-pressure steam.
- iii. **Mechanical Energy:** A turbine is exposed to high-pressure steam, which rotates it. It is from this turbine rotation that thermal energy is transformed into mechanical energy by the rotating turbine.

- iv. Electricity Generation: when an electric generator with moving wire coils inside a magnetic field is coupled to a rotating turbine. Electrical power is produced when this movement creates an electric current.

Now, once electricity is generated, it is typically transmitted through high voltage to substations. Now these stations encompass the three stages of electricity supply, such as Generation, transmission and distribution. When electricity is generated, it is transmitted using transmission lines over distances. These lines are usually constructed between transmission substations located at electric generating stations, supported either on towers or buried underground. Recall that electricity power is sent out to these lines at a very high voltage. This power transmitted moves through these lines into the distribution systems located in the local service territories. It is this distribution system that connects the transmission system to the customer's equipment. At this stage of distribution, the high transmitted electrical voltage reduces, further, a distribution transformer reduces the voltage. Hence, the transmission and distribution substations are installations where the voltage, phase or other attributes of the electrical energy are reduced as part of the final process of distribution to homes and industries (Crane and Fox, 2011).

The transmission lines that are used in Nigeria to supply power are in three phases, which are the alternating current (AC), single-phase AC current and high-voltage direct current (DC) systems. Alternators generate electricity using the same principle as DC generators; however, AC's advantage over DC is that it can easily be stepped down by a transformer, thus reducing its voltage in the realm of power distribution. According to Hassan (2014), Using stepped-up and stepped-down voltages and currents is significantly more efficient when transporting electrical power over long distances for usage by industry, businesses, or consumers. To ensure that electricity reaches

consumers, a massive network of interconnected power plants, transmission lines, substations, and distribution lines makes up the complete electrical grid.

A reliable and sufficient supply of electricity is essential for industrial processes, and it plays a significant role in determining the productivity and efficiency of manufacturing and production activities. Therefore, Energy efficiency is a paramount concern for industries, impacting both cost and environmental sustainability. Efficient electricity generation, transmission, and utilization methods are crucial for industrial facilities. This includes optimizing equipment, using advanced control systems, and adopting energy-saving technologies to minimize energy waste. There is a big environmental impact associated with the energy sources used to generate power. Concerns about their carbon footprint are growing among many industries, and to cut greenhouse gas emissions, they may favour electricity produced from clean, renewable sources. Integrating renewable energy solutions into industrial operations indicates this shift towards sustainability of not just the industries alone but also the environment in which they operate (Oyedepo, 2012).

2.1.2. The Concept of Capacity Utilization

Capacity reflects the instantaneous ability to provide the energy required to do work (such as generator capability to provide electricity, transmission capability to transmit electricity, etc.) (Energy dynamics, 2023). A plant's capacity refers to the maximum amount of electricity that a power plant or a power system can produce at a given time. It is measured in watts (W) or megawatts (MW). Power generation capacity utilization refers to the percentage of a power plant's maximum output that is being used. It is a measure of how efficiently a power plant is being utilized. A high-capacity utilization rate indicates that a power plant is being used effectively,

while a low-capacity utilization rate indicates that there is excess capacity that is not being used. The United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (2021) also defined the concept of “capacity utilization” as a percentage representing the extent to which a generating unit fulfilled its capacity to generate electric power over a given period.

In many developing nations, underutilization of power plants is a common issue due to inefficient management, lack of fuel, and aging infrastructure. This leads to energy shortages and frequent outages, which have a negative impact on industrial productivity. Industries that are heavily reliant on a stable power supply for operations, such as manufacturing and mining, are particularly vulnerable to these disruptions. Improving capacity utilization through better management and investment in modern technologies is essential for enhancing industrial productivity.

Over the previous 40 years, electricity generated in Nigeria has encompassed everything from gas-fired, oil-fired, and hydroelectric power plants to coal-fired, with the hydroelectric and gas-fired systems taking primacy. With an installed capacity of approximately 12,522 MW, Nigeria generates most of its power through thermal and hydro. The country's current installed capacity is approximately 13,000 megawatts, but because of numerous failures across the value chain, only about 3,800 megawatts are evacuated for consumption (ITA, 2023).

An analysis of the latest 2022 Electricity Market Competition Report by The PUNCH (2023) showed that the country’s available power capacity dropped from 6,401MW in 2015 to 4,059MW in 2022 (Nnodim, 2023). Several factors can affect generation capacity utilization, cause generation of electricity to fall, and transmission to have bottlenecks and distribution inefficient, including:

1. **Rapidly Growing Demand:** This issue sprung up with the development of industrialization in Nigeria, coupled with the increase in the country's population and the need for industrial output to meet the nation's economic demand, which a corresponding additional power plant did not progressively meet. Electricity demand varies throughout the day, the week, and the year. When demand is high, power plants need to operate at higher capacity to meet demand.
2. **The availability of generation resources:** These resources, such as coal, natural gas, and renewable energy, can also affect capacity utilisation. If there is a shortage of generation resources, power plants may be unable to operate at full capacity.
3. **Power plant efficiency also affects generation capacity utilisation.** More efficient power plants can produce more electricity with less fuel, which can help reduce excess capacity.
4. **Inadequate Data:** One of the major challenges facing electricity in Nigeria today is that there is inadequate basic validated data on electricity demand, supply, ATC and C losses, etc. The lack of accurate data has plunged planning and investment attempts in the power sector.
5. **Poor and Inadequate Maintenance:** Furthermore, electricity generation capacity in Nigeria is being challenged by a lack of power infrastructure maintenance and outdated power plants (Ibebuike and Okeke, 2020). Some sections of the National Grid are outdated, with poor and inadequate maintenance equipment.
6. **Poor Utilization of Existing Assets:** Given the unreliable grid energy, Nigeria's thriving generator market exists. There is a growing uptake of off-grid solar power installations to replace expensive diesel generators nationwide for commercial and industrial applications. Over 50 MW of solar capacity has been installed over the last five years. Also, the Nigerian government issued the Sustainable Energy for All Action Agenda (SEforAll) targets, which

aim to achieve a 20% and 19% contribution of solar energy to Nigeria's electricity generation mix by 2020 and 2030, respectively.

The measurement of electricity generation plays a crucial role in understanding the capacity and output of power-producing facilities. The progression of units reflects the increasing scale and capacity of power generation, particularly in the context of a country like Nigeria. Electricity generation in Nigeria, as in many parts of the world, is typically measured in units of electrical power. The standard unit for measuring power is the watt (W) (US EIA, 2022). In the context of electricity generation, the watt is often used in conjunction with multiples or submultiples to express larger or smaller quantities of power.

Furthermore, a broader term that encompasses vast and indivisible power that fuels our world is the "megawatt" In addition to megawatts, electricity generation can also be measured in gigawatts (GW), which is equivalent to one thousand megawatts. Gigawatts are commonly used for larger-scale electricity generation projects, such as those involving hydropower dams or nuclear power plants. These units of measurement quantify the rate at which electricity is generated, consumed, or transmitted, providing a crucial metric for understanding the energy landscape of nations and the global energy scenario (Stein, 2023

The journey from watts to gigawatts in electricity generation measurement encapsulates the evolution of power production from small-scale systems to national grids. The watt, kilowatt, megawatt, and gigawatt serve as benchmarks that facilitate the comprehension and communication of power capacities at various scales. In the context of a dynamic country like Nigeria, these units

play a pivotal role in shaping energy policies, assessing infrastructure development, and working towards a sustainable and resilient energy future.

2.1.3. The Concept of Electricity Supply

Frenzeljr (2010) defined a power supply as an essential component that provides electric power to electrical devices, converting energy from an outlet into usable form. Most circuit setups require either DC or AC power to function effectively. Brandt et al. (2017) opine that Electricity supply delivers electrical power to consumers via a grid system, ensuring an equilibrium between power generation and demand from diverse sources, including fossil fuels and renewable energy. It encompasses centralized and self-sufficient local electricity supply systems, which can operate independently or be linked to a larger regional or national grid.

The operation definition for this study conceptualizes power supply as the process of delivering electricity from power generation plants to end-users. This process involves the transmission of electricity over long distances and its distribution to homes, businesses, and industries. Power supply systems consist of transmission lines, transformers, substations, and distribution lines that ensure electricity reaches its final destination.

In the context of industrial productivity, the reliability and consistency of the power supply are critical. An unreliable power supply characterized by frequent outages, voltage fluctuations, and poor quality of electricity can severely hinder industrial operations. Power interruptions can damage industrial equipment, reduce the efficiency of production processes, and lead to increased costs due to downtime. Moreover, industries that experience inconsistent power supply are forced

to invest in alternative energy sources, such as diesel generators, which increases operational costs and reduces competitiveness.

The infrastructure required for efficient power supply is complex and capital-intensive. Developing countries often face significant challenges in maintaining and upgrading their transmission and distribution networks, resulting in frequent power losses and inefficiencies. These inefficiencies can lead to a widening gap between electricity demand and supply, further undermining industrial productivity. To improve the power supply, governments must invest in expanding and modernizing grid infrastructure to reduce transmission losses and enhance the reliability of electricity delivery.

2.1.4 The Concept of Government Expenditure

According to Muguro (2017), Government expenditure is the expenses incurred by a nation's government on the collective needs of a country (Muguro, 2017). As per Danladi et al. (2015), government expenditure refers to the money that government spends in an economy occurring at every tier of government. Gukat and Oboru, (2017) also defined the concept as what it costs the government to provide and maintain itself as an institution, the economy and society. They further explained that as economic activities become more and more evolved and large, government spending will also increase. Another definition was given by Taiwo (2012), who opined that government expenditure is a fiscal policy that is wielded to control inflation, unemployment, depression, balance of payment, and foreign exchange rates.

In Nigeria, Federal government expenditures are broadly divided into two broad categories: capital and recurrent expenditure. Recurrent expenditures consist of regular government spending on

administrative operations like workers' wages and salaries, goods and services, loans, maintenance of public equipment, and other administrative expenses. On the other hand, capital expenditures are spent on development projects or investments such as roads and bridges, health, education, electricity generation, telecommunication, water, etc. The role of the Nigerian government in economic activities has grown enormously, and the challenges that public policymakers face are increasing daily. Public expenditures have been growing continuously over the years, especially in the last two decades following the ever-increasing population of the nation.

the Keynesian Economics School of thought, the attention of a significant number of nations has been drawn to the importance of government involvement in stabilising and regulating aggregates of the general economy. Hence, the days of John Maynard Keynes (1926) can be said to be the origin of the discussions regarding how government funds are allocated, a time when government intervention was called for to alleviate the negative impacts of market failures in managing the macroeconomy of nations after the World War I and the approaching War II. It was opined that private individuals were not efficient in allocating resources after the war, and their existing businesses were destroyed as a result of the war. On the other hand, people could no longer exert purchasing power as no business activity which made industries lay off workers during the period of war, hence no earnings for consumers. Sequel to this little or no economic and social activities in nations,

Keynes, therefore, called for the government's attention to allocate its resources to provide social facilities and develop public organisations to keep the economy afloat (Enofe et al., 2014). Additionally, the Great Depression of 1929-1933 led to a new wave of expansionist public spending policies. A period regarded as a failure of the Laissez-Faire. Thus, the public authority

was required to play an active role in the economic and social activities of the nation to influence macroeconomic processes, correct cyclic developments, predict and prevent further crises or make plans to counter their negative impacts.

Following Keynes's postulations, followers of his doctrines arose, developing diverse models and identifying public financial policy types that exist to alleviate the macro economy of nations by stimulating aggregate demand. They stated that public expenditure has helped to increase the employment rate as well as the production rate. Additionally, they postulated that public expenditure remains a means of economic and social intervention, as continuous use of public funds to fund the state's administrative tasks can increase the production capacity of an economy (Enofe et al., 2014). Bostan and Petrisor (2012) captured this trend in government expenditure in their journal "Reconsiderations of the Modern Concepts of Public Expenditure in the Current Development Context". The authors focused on the main aspects of the contemporary concept of government expenditure by giving interpretations in terms of economic evolution over the years. A concept emanating from the relationship with the human development index has now grown into a topic that plays a great role in the efficient allocation and distribution of resources in a nation.

Furthermore, Bostan and Petrisor (2012) argued that the characteristics of modern interpretation of public spending are that they are recognised as processes for reallocating their use consistent with certain socio-economic optimum. Thus, the reallocation of financial resources through government spending is not seen as a resource consumption but as an investment similar to the capitalists. They also opined that the modern vision of public expenditure interpretation is observed to be linked to specific actions financed via public expenditure budget, reflecting in the concrete structure and size, although, to some degree, political choices are those that dictate often

without regard to economic requirements. Thus, the issue of public expenditure has become a field of wide interest among management decision-makers, especially at the macroeconomic level, in the context of their integration into models of economic growth.

Government expenditure trended from the need to promote welfare, provide social and economic aid to disadvantaged consumers, and combat private sector failures by producing public goods, social amenities and infrastructure. The 1980s, however, saw the return of a predominantly market-determined economy with emphasis on the cut of government spending. The monetarism postulations of Friedman (1998) were fuelled by this advocacy, which contended for cuts in government expenditures, tight monetary policy, deregulation of and opening of competition of public monopolies with the privatization of most public enterprise. It is on this economic conceptual clarification on government expenditure that this present study connects it to government expenditure on electricity. That is public spending on electrical infrastructure that supports one of the objectives of this study. What then is the operation definition of government expenditure for this present study? Government expenditure on electricity refers to the funds allocated by the government to support the production, transmission, and distribution of electricity. This includes spending on infrastructure projects, such as power plants and transmission lines, as well as subsidies and other forms of financial assistance to the electricity sector.

2.1.5 The Concept of Industrial Productivity

Industrial productivity is a crucial concept in economics, as it measures the efficiency with which an industrial sector utilizes its resources to produce goods and services. It is typically expressed as the output of goods and services per unit of input, such as labour, capital, or energy. Industrial productivity is a key determinant of economic growth, competitiveness, and overall prosperity

(Kenton et al. 2023). Tangen, (2002) defined Industrial productivity as the output of goods and services per unit of input, such as labour or capital. It measures how efficiently a country's industries use their resources to produce goods and services. A high level of industrial productivity indicates that a country is producing more goods and services with fewer resources, while a low level of industrial productivity indicates that a country is producing fewer goods and services with more resources (Priya and Aroulmoji, 2020). Various factors affect industrial productivity, including:

1. **Technology:** The adoption of advanced technologies, such as automation, robotics, and digitalization, can significantly enhance productivity by streamlining production processes, reducing labour costs, and improving product quality.
2. **Infrastructure:** Reliable and efficient infrastructure, including power supply, transportation networks, and communication systems, is essential for smooth industrial operations and efficient resource utilization.
3. **Human Capital:** A skilled and knowledgeable workforce is crucial for operating complex technologies, implementing innovative production techniques, and adapting to changing market demands.
4. **Management Practices:** Effective management practices, such as lean manufacturing, supply chain optimization, and quality control, can significantly improve resource utilization, reduce waste, and enhance overall productivity.
5. **Government Policies:** Government policies that promote technological innovation, invest in infrastructure, support human capital development, and foster a competitive business environment can positively impact industrial productivity.

The process of Industrialization, as we now know, entails systems change or advancing the production process from a local to a technologically automated process for efficiency in the production of goods and services. Hence, the need for a constant energy supply to this sector cannot be overemphasized. For these industries, the supply alone does not cut it, the cost of electricity itself is also another critical factor, as the entire cost of running an industrial facility can be greatly impacted by the cost of power generation, distribution, and tariffs (Akinbola, 2018). The prevailing challenges of the power sector in Nigeria as earlier discussed in this chapter, attributed to factors like preventive and routine maintenance of the national power generation facilities, operational problems, corruption, etc., have no doubt resulted in huge energy losses and several major breakdowns in the sector such as the trending power grid collapsing disrupting the pace of industrial development in Nigeria.

2.1.6 Energy Sources for Electricity

According to Alam (2006), “energy is an indispensable force driving all economic activities”. This implies that for more economic activity to go on in a country, greater energy must be generated and consumed to attain a strong economy. Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) are believed to be the engine room for the development of any economy because they form the bulk of business activities in a growing economy like that of Nigeria, and they contribute to GDP and employment generation capacity. A major problem for SMEs in Nigeria is inadequate and inefficient utilities such as power supply, which tend to escalate operation costs as SMEs resort to private provisioning of such utilities. Studies have shown that Nigeria’s abysmally poor electricity supply adds 40% to the costs of goods produced (Adenikinju, 2005). These high production costs have compelled many industries, for example, Dunlop tyres and other industrial corporations, to

either shut down or relocate to neighbouring countries, thereby deterring domestic and international investment. Also, apart from its direct fiscal effects, the power sector is strategic for increasing the competitiveness of the Nigerian economy by reducing overall energy costs and facilitating the modernisation of the technology used by economic agents and businesses (Akinbola, 2018). It is therefore important to investigate how efficient power supply has been in ensuring effective industrial development in Nigeria.

1. Fossil Fuel

Fossil fuels are energy resources collected from the remains of living organisms that have been altered and buried by sediments and exposed to pressures and temperatures that have been elevated for a long time (Gerali, 2021). They are often classified as non-renewable energy sources because they are depleting. Fossil fuels are Nigeria's most dominant energy source, and they can be quickly exhaustible, exerting a negative impact on the environment where they are converted or used and even beyond. This is because when fossil fuels are used as a reliable source of energy, they release greenhouse gases, contributing to climate change and air pollution. Fossil fuel reserves are finite, raising concerns about future energy security. What is even worse about fossil fuels is the fact that they could also be made temporarily obsolete due to their price and/or availability.

With the continuous rise in the world's population and growth in economies coupled with industrial activities, there has been a high demand for energy in homes and industries. Hence, fossil fuels could no longer meet this exponential rise in demand without taking a great toll on the biosphere (Chilakpu, 2015). Nigeria depends mostly on fossil fuel sources for power generation, but the country also employs some hydropower to meet its electricity needs. In 2012, natural gas

and oil comprised about two-thirds of the thermal power generated. This contributed to her ranking as 46th globally for Carbon-di-oxide (CO₂) emissions, having a recorded release of about 73.69 metric tons of the gas into her atmosphere in 2011(Meisen, 2014). However, while Nigeria had a total electricity capacity of 11.7 gigawatts (GW), in 2012, the country generated about 31.5 gigawatt-hours (GWh) in 2021, and about 74% of that total was derived from fossil fuel sources, and the remainder from hydropower (EIA, 2022). The Fossil fuels used as energy resources today in Nigeria are natural gas, coal, and coal, although other enormous resources of fossil fuel exist, we would look at the highlighted ones.

- i. **Natural Gas Power Generation:** Natural gas is a fuel used by heat engines which produces the energy with which electricity is generated from the turbine. Natural gas is a mixture of hydrocarbon and non-hydrocarbon gases found in formations below the surface of the earth (Wan-Abu-Barka and Ali, 2010). Natural gas holds a dominant position in Nigeria's energy sector, accounting for about 80% of the total electricity generated for the national grid, while the other 14% is generated by hydropower plants (Ekpu and Olusegun, 2020). Abundant reserves, primarily in the Niger Delta region, make it a readily available and cost-effective fuel for power generation. Gas-fired power plants have become the workhorses of the nation's electricity supply, supplying a substantial portion of Nigeria's energy needs (Roche et al., 2017; Occhiali and Falchetta 2018).
- ii. **Coal Power Generation:** Coal is expected to remain one of the dominant fuels in global electricity power generation as a result of its low cost, high reliability and high availability (Denloye, and Akinola, 2016). According to Nigeria Coal Corporation data, Coal exploration in Nigeria started as far back as 1916, and it has records showing that sub-bituminous stream

coals are available in more than 22 coalfields spread over 13 States in Nigeria. The proven coal reserves are about 639 million metric tonnes while the inferred reserves are about 2.75 billion metric tonnes. Although Coal has played a role in Nigeria's energy mix, it has yet to make a significant contribution to Nigeria's power generation due to environmental concerns as it produces toxic gases which are hazardous to human health and the environment; and a global shift toward cleaner energy sources (Denloye, and Akinola, 2016). The process of converting coal to electricity involves the milling of the coal to a fine powder, and its combustion in a boiler to generate steam to drive. The combustion process in the boiler generates gaseous emissions by the thermal decomposition of the coal. These gases include sulphur dioxide SO₂, nitrogen oxides (NO₂), carbon dioxide (CO₂), mercury, and other chemical by-products that vary depending on the type of coal being used (Moretti and Jones, 2012). These emissions are the factors responsible for certain environmental and health hazards such as acid rain, lung cancer, and cardiovascular diseases.

- iii. **Crude Oil Power Generation:** According to Oniemola (2015) electricity generation is dominated by oil and gas. However, the utilization of oil use is limited due to the higher operating costs compared to natural gas and environmental considerations. Like its fellow fossil fuels coal and natural gas, crude oil is combustible, which means it can be burned. When burned in an oil-fired power plant, it can heat water past its boiling point to produce steam, which can be used to spin turbines in order to generate electricity. The oil is burned to heat water and produce steam. This steam propels the blades of a turbine. This is attached to a generator, which produces electricity. Additionally, burning oil produces a lot of air pollution, which can be dangerous to surrounding communities. It also emits large amounts

of greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide and methane, which contribute to climate change (Tara Energy, 2022).

2. Renewable Energy

According to Agbo et al., (2021), an energy which source is essentially inexhaustible is referred to as a renewable energy. This means that these sources of energy are naturally restored, and they are unlimited, replenishing rapidly (Uyigüe, et. Al., 2007). With the need for a more sustainable energy future growing atomically, Nigeria embarked on a journey to incorporate renewable energy sources into its electricity generation mix, this is because fossil fuels are not only non-renewable, but they also cost more and have adverse impact on the environment. Solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, hydro and all other sources of energy that can be obtained either directly or indirectly from the sun's energy are classified as renewable energy renewable and they are indefinitely replenished by nature. In Nigeria, the developments in solar and wind power are gradually increasing with the discovery of their high potential and benefits for Nigeria's environment and society (Benchmac, et al., 2019). By 2006, the Nigerian government initiated the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) aimed at increasing the supply of renewable electricity (wind, solar, biomass and small hydro) from 13% of total installed electricity generation capacity in 2015 to 23% in 2025 and 36% by 2030 (Gerretsen, 2018).

The global wind and solar power capacity built in 2014 stood at about 100 gigawatts (GW) compared to the 74GW built in 2013 (EcoWatch, 2015). emerged as the leading investor in renewal energy followed by the United States. In 2014, wind production accounted for 39.1 per cent of Denmark's overall electricity generation from the clean energy sources, thus breaking a new global

record. This excellent performance is an indication that the country will meet its aspiration of generating 50 per cent of its power from renewal sources in 2020 (CBN bulletin, 2015). Currently, Nigeria generates a small amount of energy from renewable sources such as hydropower, solar, wind and biomass (Aliyu, et al., 2018).

The Nigerian government has embraced the use of renewable sources such as biomass and solar to produce electricity mostly for rural and semi-urban areas that are out of the reach of distribution companies. Through the Rural Electrification Agency, the federal government has actively been commissioning electrification projects since 2014, using solar energy as the main source of renewable electricity. According to the agency's impact report released in January 2019, the REA recorded over 99,450 connections in a 20-month period and sourced over \$550 million in funding for investment in rural areas and market areas in the country. The following discussions uncover the different kinds of renewable energy available in Nigeria.

- i. Solar Power Generation:** This entails the utilization of sunlight for electricity generation. This can be attained directly through photovoltaics (PVs), depicting the process in which energy from the sun as photons strikes surfaces to bring about electronic movement (photoelectric effect). Another method is by utilizing the sun indirectly to focus its energy to cause water to heat or solar collectors, which can then produce power; this method is also known as the concentration of solar power (Agbo et al., 2021). Solar power plants are a rapidly growing source of electricity generation in Nigeria, with their share of the country's total electricity production increasing from 20 gigawatt hours of renewable source used in 2012 to about 40-gigawatt hours used in 2020 for electricity production in the country. in 2010 to 1.5% in 2023. Solar power plants convert sunlight directly into electricity (Sasu, 2023).

The continent of Africa is the largest in the world in terms of daily yearly sunshine, with an average of 6.25 hours, according to the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) (2019 Nigerian Energy Report). Furthermore, Nigeria is a tropical country with an average daily sunshine hour range of 3.5 hours in the coastal regions and 9.0 hours in the northern regions. Nigeria is located between 4- and 13 degrees latitude with a landmass of roughly 9.24×10^5 km². Awogbemi and Komolafe (2011) provided evidence for this claim, stating that approximately 4.851×10^{12} kWh of energy is obtained in Nigeria from solar radiation. The average annual incident solar energy in Nigeria is 1.804×10^{15} kWh, calculated using the country's land area and an average of 5.535 kWh/m²/day. Approximately 27 times the country's total conventional energy resources are represented in energy units by this annual solar energy insolation number. Accordingly, Nigeria has an endless supply of solar energy to harness.

- ii. **Hydro Power Generation:** Hydropower, or hydro, is the oldest and most extensively used renewable energy source that uses water flow to generate electricity. Since the water's storage level differs from the tailwater to which it is discharged, power is believed to be generated from the potential energy present in the water (Manohar and Adeyanju, 2009). Hydropower is produced when electricity generators are used to extract energy from moving water. At the end of its passage down the pipes, the falling water causes turbines to rotate (Hassan, 2014). The turbines, in turn, drive generators, which convert the turbines' mechanical energy into electricity. Transformers are then used to convert the alternating voltage suitable for the generators to a higher voltage suitable for long-distance transmission. The structure that houses the turbines and generators, and into which the pipes or penstocks feed, is called the powerhouse (Britannica, 2023). Hydroelectric power plants are usually located in dams that

impound rivers, thereby raising the water level behind the dam and creating as high a head as feasible.

iii. Wind Power Generation: Wind energy, or wind power as it is also known, is a form of renewable energy that uses airflow to generate electricity. Wind power plants convert the kinetic energy of wind into electricity. Now, in order to transform the energy in the moving air into mechanical energy, turbines, generators, and dynamos can be used (Vincent and Yusuf, 2014). A single small wind turbine can generate electricity for a single home, while many larger turbines lined up together on wind farms can generate electricity for the grid. The wind turns the blades of a wind turbine that is connected to a generator, and the generator converts the wind's kinetic energy to electricity. Nigeria has great potential for onshore wind power generation (Owoeye, 2017). However, wind power plants are a relatively small source of electricity generation in Nigeria, accounting for less than 1% of the country's total electricity production.

iv. Biomass Power Generation: Biomass energy refers to the energy of biological systems such as wood and other biological materials. Biomass is considered to be carbon neutral due to no net gain in atmospheric CO₂ when the fuel is burned. Many technologies have been designed to turn biomass into efficient, clean and sustainable energy, including direct combustion, co-firing, biomass gasification and anaerobic digestion, which involves using micro-organisms to break down the biomass and turn it into biogas (Olaoye, et al., 2016). Through the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited (NNPC), the Nigerian government has a renewable energy division exploring biomass opportunities in the sector and has a mandate to expand the automotive biofuels industry. NNPCCL intends for projects to be executed as a public-private partnership (PPP) model, with NNPCCL as a minority shareholder. Plans include using

sugarcane and cassava as key biomass raw materials. However, this has stalled due to a lack of appropriate legislative framework and appropriate equity financing.

Solid biomass and waste account for approximately 80% of total primary energy consumed in Nigeria (Eweka, et al., 2022). A study by Simonyan and Fasina (2013) explored the annual bioenergy potential for each source of biomass in Nigeria. Examples of Biomass includes, agricultural residues and wood, human and animal waste, food and feed processing waste, energy crops etc. Biomass energy is known to contributes to local electricity needs and supports sustainability in these regions (Simonyan, 2013). According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration, most Nigerians, especially rural dwellers, use biomass and waste from wood, charcoal, and animal dung, to meet their energy needs. Biomass accounts for about 80% of the total primary energy consumed in Nigeria. Most of these go towards heating, lighting, and cooking in rural areas.

- v. **Geothermal Energy:** Geothermal energy is generated from the earth's crust which is transported through cracks and fractures in the host rocks and its natural fluids at temperatures above the ambient level (Kelechi, and Owoka, 2023). Nigeria has identified areas with geothermal potential, primarily in the northeastern part of the country. The presence of volcanic activity and geothermal manifestations, such as hot springs, indicates the possibility of utilizing geothermal energy. While geothermal energy may not be a major contributor to Nigeria's electricity generation at present, the country has shown interest in increasing its overall renewable energy capacity. Policies and initiatives have been introduced to encourage the development of renewable energy sources, including geothermal, to diversify the energy mix and enhance sustainability. However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of geothermal energy in Nigeria. The government's commitment

to renewable energy development and advancements in geothermal technology suggest that geothermal energy could play an increasingly important role in Nigeria's energy landscape in the future (Eyinla, et al., 2016)

- vi. Nuclear Power:** Nuclear power is electricity generated by power plants that derive their heat from fission in a nuclear reactor. Except for the reactor, which plays the role of a boiler in a fossil-fuel power plant, a nuclear power plant is similar to a large coal-fired power plant, with pumps, valves, steam generators, turbines, electric generators, condensers, and associated equipment (Martin, 2023). Nuclear power currently accounts for about 10% of the world's electricity generation. The future of nuclear power is uncertain due to its challenges. However, some countries, such as France and China, are continuing to invest in nuclear power, while others, such as Germany and Japan, have moved away from it. The potential of nuclear power to provide a reliable, carbon-free source of electricity has gained traction in Nigeria. Nuclear power plants utilize the heat generated from nuclear reactions to produce electricity, offering a means to meet growing electricity demands without emitting greenhouse gases. In 2004, the Nigerian government established the Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Authority (NNRA) to oversee the development and regulation of nuclear power in the country. The government also signed an agreement with Russia to build a nuclear power plant in Kogi State. However, the project has faced delays and cost overruns, and its future remains uncertain. Furthermore, the development of nuclear power in Nigeria faces significant challenges, including the high capital costs associated with building and operating nuclear power plants, as well as the safety concerns and radioactive waste management issues. Public perception of nuclear power remains mixed, with concerns over safety and potential environmental risks (IEA, 2019).

2.2. Theoretical Review

In the literature, some theories try to explain the link between energy and economic growth and other components, such as investment or industrial growth. However, among the several theoretical lenses that scholars have employed in their investigations on power generation and industrial productivity, this present study highlights the neoclassical growth, which demonstrates the role of energy as a fundamental input for industrial production, emphasising the positive correlation between energy availability and economic output; secondly, the second law of thermodynamics which states how energy is involved in transforming input to output; the stern model, the Olduvai theory of energy production and population; and the intervention theory about public finance

2.2.1. Neoclassical Theory of Growth

Robert Solow, a Nobel laureate in economics, is considered the main developer of the neoclassical growth model. He introduced the model in 1956, building on earlier work by Ramsey, and it has become a fundamental framework for understanding long-run economic growth. The neoclassical theory of growth is an economic framework that focuses on the long-term determinants of economic growth. It emphasizes the role of technology, capital accumulation, and labour in driving economic expansion that is This involves the total output within the economy with respect to the aggregate amount of labour, physical capital and human capital in an economy (Wilson, 2021). More specifically to electricity generation, the neoclassical theory of growth can be applied to analyse the factors that contribute to the expansion of the electricity generation sector. This includes examining how technological advancements and capital investment in power plants and

infrastructure can help improve productivity and efficiency, all of which play a role in increasing electricity generation capacity (Okungbowa and Abhulimen, 2021).

In practical terms, the neoclassical theory of growth can be used to assess how investments in new technologies, such as renewable energy sources or more efficient power generation methods, can impact the overall growth of an economy through an increase in industrial productivity. By applying neoclassical growth theory to electricity generation, policymakers and industry stakeholders can gain insights into fostering sustainable and efficient growth in the electricity sector while considering factors such as capital investment and technological progress to augment labour productivity (Banton, 2019). The neoclassical theory of economic growth, therefore, provides a framework for understanding the relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity in this present study. With apriori expectation that an increase in electricity generation capacity would lead to higher industrial productivity through the several channels explained

2.2.2. The Theory of Thermodynamics

Thermodynamics developed out of a desire to increase the efficiency of early steam engines. Historically, the second law was an empirical finding accepted as an axiom of thermodynamic theory. The second law of thermodynamics was developed in the mid-19th century by Scottish physicist William Thomson and German physicist Rudolf Clausius around 1860. In 1850, recognized the need for a second law to explain the irreversibility of some processes and the concept of energy not being fully recoverable. They independently formulated the key principles of the second law based on earlier work by other scientists. The theoretical literature on the second

law of thermodynamics holds that a minimum energy quantity is necessary to transform matter (Jeffery and Taylor, 2018). As a result, other production components must be limited in their energy substitution (Stern, 2012). Because production begins with inputs or raw materials being transformed into output or finished products, it, therefore, depicts that all manufacturing or production processes necessitate energy use. Thus, ecological economics regard energy as a necessary input of production. No mechanised production can proceed without energy conversion, according to the rule of thermodynamics. As a result, we anticipate that the corresponding energy source will have a favourable association with industrial output (Okungbwa and Abhulimen, 2021)

2.2.3. Olduvai Theory of Energy Production and Population

Richard C. Duncan, an author, first proposed the Olduvai theory in 1989, under the title "The pulse-transient theory of industrial civilization." Later this theory was supplemented in 1993 with the article "The life-expectancy of industrial civilisation: The decline to global equilibrium." Expanding his original ideas by providing more insights regarding the life expectancy of industrial civilization. The Olduvai Theory of energy production and population is a hypothetical framework that attempts to explain the relationship between energy consumption, population growth, and economic development. It was proposed by British economist David Fleming in 1981 and is based on the idea that there is a finite amount of energy available on Earth and that as the population grows, so does the demand for energy. According to the Olduvai Theory, as the population increases, so does the demand for energy. This increased demand for energy leads to the depletion of non-renewable resources, such as fossil fuels, and the degradation of the environment. As a result, economic growth slows down and eventually stops. However, this theory holds great

insights into the relationship between energy, population, and economic growth (Allaki, et al., 2019).

The Olduvai theory suggestions are known to be based on world energy and population data, thus stating that the life expectancy of Industrial Civilization is less than or equal to 100 years. The theory explains the 1979 peak and subsequent decline in energy production per capita, which is expected to fall to its 1930 value by 2030 (Duncan, 2001). The collapse of Industrial Civilization could be attributed to an "epidemic" of permanent blackouts of high-voltage electric power networks worldwide. Although Duncan has argued that the Olduvai theory may be proven wrong, at present, it cannot be rejected by the historic world energy production and population data. However, one downplays of this theory is that it did not take into cognizance the potential for technological advancements to improve energy efficiency and reduce environmental impacts as the world now drifts to sustain the earth.

2.2.4. Intervention Theory About Public Finance

The interventionist theory in economics is a school of thought that advocates for government intervention in the economy to correct market failures and promote economic growth. Interventionist policies can include fiscal measures, such as government spending and taxation, as well as regulatory measures, such as antitrust laws and environmental regulations (Wiley, 1968). Richard Musgrave is a prominent economist who proposed the intervention theory about public finance in his 1959 book "The Theory of Public Finance: A Study in Public Economy". Musgrave argued that government intervention in the economy is necessary to address market failures and achieve socially desirable outcomes. Thus, this theory depicts the efficacy rationale for

government intervention, arguing that it can maximize an economy's output and move it back onto its production possibility frontier. Interventionist policies can also be used to promote economic growth. By investing in infrastructure, education, and research, the government can help create long-term economic growth conditions. Additionally, government intervention can help to stabilize the economy during periods of economic downturn. Keynes' "General Theory" supports government intervention during economic turmoil, stating that full employment can only occur if there is a boost from public investments and government policies. During an economic depression, governments can boost demand by spending much cash, as resources are idle and insufficient (Filho and Terra, 2012).

2.3 Empirical Review

The impact of electrical supply on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria has received substantial research, albeit with conflicting outcomes. To ascertain the effect of electricity consumption and its implications on industrial performance in Nigeria, Basse, Anagha, and Ikpe (2022) obtained time series data, which they used to carry out empirical analysis. The study finds that a unit rise in industrial electricity consumption and exchange rate contributes positively to industrial performance. However, a percentage increase in gross fixed capital formation and gross domestic product reduces industrial performance. The study concludes that irregular electricity supply has weakened industrial performance in Nigeria and recommends a well-rounded energy mix to complement existing energy sources.

In Nwankwo and Njogo (2013) a multiple regression model was adopted to examine the effect of electricity supply on economic development and also on industrial development in Nigeria from

1970 to 2010. The research variables were gross fixed capital formation, industrial production, and population. The findings show that electricity supply, gross fixed capital formation, and industrial production positively affect economic development. The study recommends prioritising issues related to electricity production and industrial development in the budget scheme to facilitate economic growth in Nigeria. Similarly, As part of their specific objectives. ok, Jonah and John (2013) examined the existence of a long-run relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria. With the data obtained from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and using the multiple regression analysis, they were able to find out that there exists a long-run relationship between energy consumption and industrial output in Nigeria.

Chinedum and Nnadi (2016), investigated the impact of electricity supply on the output of the Nigerian manufacturing sector. Time series data spanning the period between 1981 and 2013 were analyzed using Johansen Cointegration and Vector Autoregression tests. The study reveals that there is a long-run relationship between electricity supply and manufacturing output in Nigeria. However, it also finds that electricity supply has an insignificant relationship with the manufacturing sector. The authors, therefore, suggested that in order for the manufacturing sector to contribute to the transformation of the Nigerian economy, there needs to be an adequate and stable electricity supply.

Ubi et al. (2012) did an econometric analysis of the determinants of electricity supply in Nigeria, having recognised it as a key constraint to industrialisation and economic development. With data from 1970 to 2009, the authors' parametric econometric analysis of ordinary least squares revealed that technology, government funding and the level of power loss were statistically significant determinants of electricity supply in Nigeria, and that an average of 40% of power is lost in

transmission per annum in Nigeria. The authors, therefore, recommended that the government should put in place measures to not only improve technology but also to protect electricity generation, transmission, and distribution equipment from being vandalized.

Nwajinka et al. (2013) examined the impact of electric energy supply on industrial productivity in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010, focusing on the extent of electricity supply's influence on industrial development and the existence of a long-term relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity. With data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin, the researchers employed multiple regression analysis. Results indicate that national energy supply does not significantly impact industrial productivity, though industrial output shows potential for future equilibrium convergence. It was therefore recommended economic growth can be supported by improving funding and management of the power sector, and fostering private partnerships

Similarly, Wilson (2021) recognized electricity supply as a major source of growth for any economy in his investigation into economic growth and electricity generation in Nigeria. The researcher examined specifically the impact of relevant factors that could affect electricity generation in Nigeria for the period 1970-2018. Using an auto-regressive distributed lag model (ARDL) approach, the study discovered that there is a direct and significant relationship between the price of electricity, economic growth, installed capacity and electricity generation in Nigeria. Wilson therefore recommended that installed capacity, price of electricity, electricity consumed, and economic growth can be utilised as a means for increasing electricity generation.

Quadri and Bukola's (2022) examine the impact of electricity consumption on manufacturing output in Nigeria from 1980 to 2021. Various diagnostic tests, like descriptive statistics, correlation

analysis, unit root tests, and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) analysis, were used. The authors obtained results which indicate that in the long run, labour, capital, and electricity consumption are the main determinants of manufacturing output in Nigeria. However, inflation and interest rates have a negative and insignificant effect on manufacturing output. In the short run, electricity consumption, labour, gross fixed capital formation, and electricity production are the key variables influencing manufacturing output. The study recommends that the government should closely monitor the privatization policy of the electricity sub-sector to ensure sufficient electricity generation and consumption to promote employment and economic growth.

Ijuo, Abraham, and Peace (2015) investigated the impact of electricity supply on the productivity of manufacturing industries in Nigeria from 1989 to 2012 with the sole aim of ascertaining the impact of electricity supply. The scholars obtained results that showed that the electricity generated and supplied covering the period under study has a positive impact on the productivity growth of manufacturing industries. However, the coefficient of this impact was observed to be very low due to inadequate and irregular supply of electricity, especially to the manufacturing subsector in the economy, resulting from the government's unnecessary spending on non-economic and unproductive sectors. Similarly, Olayemi (2012) researched how electric power outputs, supply and consumption are used to tackle low productivity. The study, which covered the period of 1970 to 2005, discovered that electricity supplied to the industrial sector was lower than that of the voltage for residential consumption.

Furthermore, Akiri et al (2015) researched the impact of electricity supply on the productivity of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria between 1980 and 2012. It highlights the critical role electricity plays in enhancing manufacturing productivity and the economy, while also addressing

the challenges of irregular and inadequate power supply in Nigeria. The study employs regression analysis to explore the relationship between manufacturing productivity and factors such as electricity generation, capacity utilization, government capital expenditure, and exchange rates. Findings indicate that while electricity supply positively impacts manufacturing productivity, inefficiencies, corruption, and poor infrastructure have limited its potential.

Chiazoka, Jonah and John (2013) conducted a study to uncover the impact of electric energy supply on industrial productivity in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010. One of the objectives of this research was to identify how electricity supply impacts industrial development in Nigeria. To attain this objective, the scholars employed multiple regression analysis, and the findings were that the national energy supply does not significantly impact industrial productivity in Nigeria. However, they suggested the need for sustained sanitization and funding of the power sector and the encouragement of private partnerships to enhance economic growth.

Moyo (2013), using data from the World Bank Enterprise survey sought to evaluate the how the quality of power infrastructure on productivity in African manufacturing firms. The author adopted the Ordinary Least Squares method to carry out his investigation and used the number of hours per day without electricity and the percentage of output lost due to outages to measure the quality of power infrastructure. The outcome of the analysis demonstrated that these variables measured were significant determinants in Uganda, Tanzania and Zambia as well as in the food and agriculture sector. The scholar further urged that the Government in Africa should implement measures to increase the reliability of power infrastructure to boost economic growth and support job creation.

Ike (2021) argued that one of Nigeria's reoccurring problems is the lack of access to electricity, both in quality and quantity. To further demonstrate his position, he investigated the impact of electricity on industrial output in Nigeria from a systems perspective. The author discovered capacity incongruencies across the power supply value chain by exploring the relationship between monthly industrial output and various aspects of the electricity delivery system, including power generation, transmission, and distribution. Pearson's correlation analysis showed no statistically significant correlation between generation capacity and transmission capacity, and there was a negative but not statistically significant correlation between transmission capacity and distribution capability. and the regression analysis results obtained show that distribution capability has a statistically significant correlation with industrial output. The study emphasizes the importance of policy development for improved electricity supply to boost the competitiveness of local industries, contribute to economic growth, and reduce poverty.

In their study, Chukwuma and King (2020) empirically examined the relationship between electricity consumption and manufacturing sector output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2019. The scholars adopted the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and considered variables such as electricity supply, labour unit, capital formation, government expenditure on power, and inflation. The findings of this research opined a stable long-run relationship between electricity consumption and manufacturing sector output. The study recommends that the government and policymakers in Nigeria focus on increasing energy generation for the manufacturing sector to promote local content and the activities of small and medium-scale enterprises.

Sani, Mukhtar and Gani (2017) contended Electricity is a necessary condition for any substantial social, economic, or modern scientific advancement in any place throughout the world. More

specifically they stated that “it is a force and engine room of the industrial sector.” In their investigation into the relationship between electricity consumption, manufacturing output, and financial development in Nigeria, they employed time series data for 1961 until 2015 which was evaluated using the Augmented Dickey-fuller (ADF) unit root test and further, Johansen and Juselius in examining the long run relationship in the model. Their findings show that instability in power supply negatively affects manufacturing efficiency and industrial output. The Granger causality test shows a causal relationship between power utilization and economic growth. The study concludes that stable electricity consumption is important for Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Altintas and Kum (2013) in their paper, analyzed the short and long-run causal link between economic development, electricity generation, exports, and prices in a multivariate model using annual data for Turkey from 1970 to 2010. Following the outcome of their research boundaries test results, there are two co-integrating connections where power generation and economic growth are the dependent variables. The findings also indicated that there is a long-run equilibrium relationship and long-term causality between economic growth, electricity generation, export, and price. Further, the researchers' study, revealed that there are bi-directional causalities in the short term between economic growth and electricity generation, and economic growth and power generation-export with a feedback effect.

Economists and policymakers have extensively studied the relationship between power generation capacity and industrial productivity, which has led to a consensus that sufficient and reliable electricity supply is essential for industrial growth and development, with claims that manufacturing processes heavily rely on electricity to operate machinery and equipment. Empirical Evidence shows numerous studies have documented the link between power generation

capacity and industrial productivity. For instance, Bassey et al. (2022) obtained results in their empirical research that depict capacity utilization to have a positive effect on industrial performance. However, the researchers stated that the findings were not statistically significant. Likewise, the results from Ijuo et al. (2015) study, in which electricity generation, capacity utilization rate, government capital expenditure on infrastructures and exchange rate were explanatory variables and productivity index as the dependent variable showed that capital utilization had a positive relationship with the productivity level of manufacturing industries in Nigeria.

A study by the International Energy Agency (IEA) found that a 1% increase in generation capacity utilization was associated with a 0.5% increase in industrial productivity. This suggests that even small increases in generation capacity utilization can have a significant impact on industrial productivity. Ogbonna, Idenyi, and Nick (2016), developed a model where Real Gross Domestic Product is a function of Power Generation capacity in Kilowatts, Gross capital formation and Unemployment to evaluate the impact of power generation capacity on economic growth in Nigeria from 1980-2015. Employing a co-integration test, vector error correction mechanism and Granger causality, the scholars obtained results which revealed that there is no causality between power generation capacity and economic growth in Nigeria during the study period. Hence, they recommended transparency in the implementation of power sector policies and oversight by the government to address corruption and improve power generation.

In an attempt to explore the determinants of capacity utilization in the Nigerian Manufacturing Sector between the years 1975 to 2008, and to ascertain the existence of long-run relationship between capacity utilization and its determinant indicators, Adeyemi and Olufemi (2016) used

Cointegration and Error Correction Model (ECM) as the estimation techniques, studying the time series properties of the research variables including capacity utilization as the dependent variable and Real Manufacturing Output Growth Rate, Real Interest Rate, Consumer's Price Index, Fixed Capital Formation in Manufacturing Sector and Electricity Generation on Rate were used as independent variables. According to the study's findings, there is a positive association between the consumer price index, fixed capital development in the manufacturing sector, and capacity utilisation. The study additionally demonstrated a negative association between generation, real manufacturing output growth rate, and capacity utilisation, resulting in a low manufacturing productivity growth rate in Nigeria.

Following the study of Baumers, Tuck, Wildman, Ashcroft and Hague, (2011) titled "Energy Inputs to Additive Manufacturing: Does Capacity Utilization Matter?", it was revealed that the effect of capacity utilization on energy efficiency empirically varies strongly across different platforms tested. Gandoor, Hinti, Jaber, and Sawalha (2008) constructed an empirical model for Jordanian industrial power use based on multivariate linear regression to identify the key drivers of electricity consumption. It was discovered that industrial production outputs and capacity utilisation are the two most important variables that affect electrical power demand, and the multivariate linear regression model can be used adequately to simulate industrial electricity consumption with a very high coefficient of determination.

The following review provides an overview of key findings, methodologies, and insights from existing research, shedding light on the critical interplay between a nation's public spending on electrical infrastructure and its industrial output. For Kolawole (2022), electricity propels growth, and therefore, his paper examined the implication of government expenditure and electricity for

economic growth using the Granger Causality, Johansen co-integration and ECM techniques over the period 1981- 2020. Findings from this study showed that the trio of electricity consumption, electricity supply and government capital expenditure have no implication whatsoever statistically for economic growth over the years under consideration.

According to Chukwuma and King (2020), the prosperity of any nation depends greatly on its energy sector; as such, the government must give prompt attention to its continuous supply for national progress and productivity to be achieved in the nation. Furthermore, they employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lagged Model (ARDL) estimation technique, and as part of the variables they considered in their investigation, government expenditure on power was found to be positively related to manufacturing sector output in Nigeria such that a unit increase in government expenditure on power will bring about proportional increase to the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Enofe, Ibeh and Ishola's (2014) study investigated the impact public expenditure on electricity has on the socio-economic development of Nigeria. They adopted the linear regression analysis model and, in the process, ran an error correction model to ascertain if there was a long-run relationship between the variables. The findings from their work demonstrate that there is, in fact, a positive relationship between government spending on electricity and the socio-economic development of Nigeria, which was largely satisfied. Hence, they suggested that the government focus on promoting efficiency in its budgetary allocation to enhance the socio-economic development of Nigeria.

Turning to the Industrial production expenditure model, Nwankwo and Njogo's (2013) regression analysis results show that electricity generation and industrial production can promote economic development, as both variables exert a positive and significant impact on economic development. More specifically, electricity generation expenditure, gross fixed capital formation, and population variables are positively related to GDP per Capita. Thus, they concluded that Electricity generation tends to improve the industrial sector if revenues are directed to the development of electricity generation.

In their paper, Orji et al (2017) examined the impact of infrastructural development on Nigeria's industrial sector, highlighting the essential role of infrastructure for the sector's survival. The research uses time series data from 1990 to 2015 and employs the ordinary least squares regression method to analyse the relationship between infrastructure and industrial performance. Results show that electricity consumption has a positive but insignificant impact on industrial performance, while gross capital formation and government spending have a negative but significant impact at a 5% confidence level. The authors therefore recommended that, to boost industrial output, improving the power sector, curbing corruption, and proper monitoring of infrastructure projects are paramount.

In Anthony and Tunde's (2014) paper the relationship between power generation/supply and industrial sector performance in Nigeria using time series data from 1975 to 2011 were examined. The variables used to test this link include the manufacturing production index, electricity generation, government capital expenditure, inflation rate, exchange rate, and capacity utilisation. The results of a series of correlation tests show that there is a positive relationship between the

index of manufacturing production and electricity generation, government capital expenditure, inflation rate, and exchange rate, but a negative relationship between capacity utilisation.

2.4. Gaps in the Literature

As earlier stated, and reviewed, there are a plethora of literary works on the impact of electricity supply on industrial productivity in Nigeria as well as other countries which have been carried out in the past, but due to the significance of the sector, there is need to update findings in tune with the prevailing challenges and opportunities that now faces both the power and industrial sectors.

Previous studies have frequently neglected to analyze the capacity utilization of electrical plants in sufficient detail. Although many of these investigations examine the impact of electricity on industrial output, they tend to focus primarily on total electricity generation and general industrial capacity utilization. This limited perspective often overlooks the significance of capacity factor and its implications for the reliability and efficiency of electricity supply.

Furthermore, unlike other scholars' works reviewed earlier, this study looks into the role of government expenditures specifically dedicated to electricity infrastructure. Also, this study has examined the composition of the energy mix, most especially as it relates to the share of renewable energy sources in Nigeria.

Summarily, this study is a major diversion from the studies of other scholars reviewed above as it goes beyond exploring the role of government expenditure on electrical infrastructure, capacity factors, and the different sources of energy and their inherent predominant effect on industrial productivity.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is the Neoclassical Growth Theory: This theory was propounded by Ramsey (1928) and further developed by Solow (1956), and the framework emphasizes the role of capital accumulation, technological advancements, and labour inputs in economic growth. You could analyze how investments in electricity infrastructure (capital) and improved capacity factors (technology) contribute to increased industrial productivity and overall economic growth. For instance, at its core, this framework recognizes that electricity is a fundamental input for many industrial processes, powering machinery, lighting factories, and enabling various manufacturing operations. The availability of reliable and efficient electricity supply directly influences the productivity and efficiency of industrial activities. The theory also argues that technological change has a major influence on an economy, and economic growth cannot continue without technological advances. There are two theories within the neoclassical framework which are:

The Solow growth theory was also known as the exogenous theory because it professed technology as an exogenous factor which determines growth. One of the basic assumptions of the Solow model is the diminishing returns to labour and capital, constant returns to scale, competitive market equilibrium, and constant savings rate. However, what is crucial about the Solow model is the fact that it explains the long-run per capita growth by the rate of technological progress, which comes from outside the model (Bala et al., 2017)

The endogenous growth theory or new growth theory was developed as a reaction to the flaws of the neoclassical (exogenous) growth theory. Romar's endogenous growth theory was first

presented in 1986 in which he considers knowledge as an input in the production function. The theory aimed at explaining the long-run growth by endogenizing productivity growth or technical progress (Stern, 2012). The major assumptions of the theory are:

- i. Increasing returns to scale because of positive externalities.
- ii. Human capital (knowledge, skills and training of individuals) and the production of new technologies are essential for long-run growth.
- iii. Private investment in research and development is the most important source of technological progress.
- iv. Knowledge or technical advances are non-rival good.

From the foregoing, we can derive the aggregate production function of the endogenous theory as follows:

$$Y=F(A, K, L) \quad \dots (3.1)$$

Where;

Y = aggregate real output.

K = stock of capital.

L = stock of labour.

A = Technology (or technological advancement).

It is worth noting that A (technological advancement) is based on the investment in research technology. Technology is seen as an endogenous factor which could be related to energy. Most technology, as given per time, is dependent on the availability of useful energy to power it. The technology referred to includes plants, machinery and the like. Without an adequate energy supply (in this case, electricity or petroleum), then, this technology is practically useless. The law of

thermodynamics helps to justify this by stating that “no production process can be driven without energy conversion”.

Energy is not the sole determinant of technology, but is necessary to ensure that technology (at whatever level) is utilized. The conversion of energy from its raw state into a useful state is highly technology-oriented. Taking a cue from the technology-oriented nature of energy production, it is also known that it is capital-intensive. Huge machinery is required to produce usable energy. This will mean that a huge amount of capital will be required to produce energy. Huge investments must then be made in energy to produce and attain energy efficiency.

In the context of the Neoclassical Growth Theory, each variable used in the study aligns with the theoretical principles that emphasise the role of capital accumulation, technological progress, and efficient resource allocation in driving economic growth and productivity. The dependent variable, industrial productivity (IND), represents the output or efficiency of the industrial sector—a direct measure of economic performance and the outcome the Neoclassical model seeks to explain.

For explanatory variables, electricity supply (ELEC) serves as a proxy for infrastructure and a critical input to production. According to the theory, access to reliable and sufficient energy boosts the productivity of capital and labour, thereby enhancing output levels. The installed capacity (INCA) variable aligns with the theory’s emphasis on technological advancement and capital deepening. Higher installed capacity reflects investments in energy infrastructure, which increases the production potential of the economy, mirroring the role of technological progress in the Solow model.

Similarly, government expenditure on electricity infrastructure (GEXP) functions as a representation of public investment in capital goods. Within the Neoclassical framework, public capital investment contributes to the formation of infrastructure that complements private production, enhances the marginal productivity of private capital, and supports long-term economic growth. By integrating these variables, the study operationalises the Neoclassical model's assertion that growth is driven by improved inputs—capital, infrastructure, and energy—which collectively support sustained increases in industrial productivity.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

A research design is a logical model of proof that helps a researcher to deduce inferences with respect to relationships that may exist among certain variables under study (Eruaga, 2019). To empirically investigate the impact of electricity generation on industrial productivity, this present study obtained a number of time series variables (such as Supply of electricity, capacity factor, government expenditure on electricity infrastructure and Industrial productivity index) ranging from 1990 to 2022 obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics. This study utilized a quantitative research design involving statistical analysis of numerical data. This approach will help the researcher identify relationships and test hypotheses. Under quantitative methods, the correlation design is well suited for this study, as it is commonly used in policy and economic research, enabling model specification.

3.2. Model Specification

The study adapted an economic model previously used by Ubi et al. (2012) and Wilson (2021) to examine the nature of the relationship between electricity supply in Nigeria and industrial productivity or output. These scholars' empirical reviews show their model to include electricity supply in Megawatts' hours, the quantity of rainfall per year in cubic centimetres, government

funding of electricity in Nigeria, the quantity of electricity lost per year in megawatts, prices of electricity per megawatts in Nigeria currency. Hence:

$$ES = f(RF, GF, PL, P) \quad \dots (3.1)$$

Where:

ES = Electricity supply in megawatt-hours

RF = Quantity of rainfall per year in cubic centimetres

GF = Government funding of electricity in Nigeria

PL = Quantity of electricity lost per year in megawatts

P = Prices of electricity per megawatt in Nigerian currency

Taking from these scholars' models, this present research formulates its model, dropping certain variables such as the Quantity of electricity lost per year, prices of electricity and quantity of electricity lost. This is because this present study focuses on key variables of interest as they relate to the research objectives, including the Supply of electricity, capacity factor, government expenditure on electricity infrastructure and Industrial productivity index. However, this present study consists of two models. The first model examines the impact of electricity supply on the Industrial Productivity Index. Further, the second model looks into the impact of capacity factor and government electricity expenditure on electricity supply; the models are therefore:

$$\text{Model 1:} \quad \text{INDP} = f(\text{ELEC}) \quad \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

$$\text{Model 2:} \quad \text{ELEC} = f(\text{INCA}, \text{GEXP}) \quad \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where:

IND = Industrial Productivity (Proxy Industrial Output);

ELEC = Electricity Generation

INCA = Installed Capacity;

GEXP = Government Expenditure on Electricity infrastructure

Equations 3.1 and 3.2 are further rewritten in a linear form:

$$ELEC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INCA_t + \beta_2 GEXP_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

$$IND_t = \beta_0 + \beta_3 ELEC_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.5)$$

Where:

t = time

β_0 = intercept

β_1 - β_3 are parameters that measure the explanatory variables' impact on the explained variable.

μ_t = error term or white noise random element, which captures other factors impacting industrial productivity that have not been captured in the specified model.

Following the theoretical literature reviewed, the *A priori expectations* of the two models were informed by theories and specified above are expressed below mathematically:

From the models, the *a priori* expectations are:

Model 1: $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$

Model 2: $\beta_3 > 0$,

3.3. Variables Measurement and Discussion

This study's variables include industrial productivity, electricity generation, capacity factor and government expenditure. The Industrial productivity index is the dependent variable in the first model, while the independent variables are electricity generation, capacity factor, and government expenditure on electricity infrastructure. However, in the second and third models, we test whether installed capacity and government expenditure impact electricity generation, which, in turn,

directly or indirectly impacts industrial productivity. The variable measurements are therefore outlined below:

1. **Industrial Output (IND):** Industrial productivity, often proxied by industrial output, measures the efficiency with which industries convert inputs (labour, capital, energy) into outputs (goods and services). A higher industrial productivity index indicates greater efficiency and competitiveness. This study utilizes industrial output to capture the industrial sector's output and the manufacturing sector's direction.

The measurement for this variable, as obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) is the Industrial Productivity Index. This index tracks the output level of Nigeria's industrial sector over time and serves as the dependent variable in the study.

2. **Electricity Generation:** Electricity generation (ELEC) is the total amount of electrical energy produced by power plants and other sources of electricity generation in MW over a specific period. A reliable and affordable supply of electricity is essential for powering machinery, lighting factories, and facilitating efficient production processes
3. **Installed Capacity:** Since electricity generation is influenced by a capacity factor, which measures the output of a power plant relative to its maximum potential output, this study's installed capacity (INCA) refers to the ratio of the electricity generated by a power plant to its maximum potential electricity generation capacity over a specific period, usually a year. It measures how efficiently a power plant operates the installed electricity capacity factors variable, an important metric for assessing power plants' performance and efficiency and planning and managing electricity generation.

4. **Government Expenditure:** Government expenditure on electricity refers to the amount of money a government spends on electricity-related activities. This can include investments in electricity generation, transmission, and distribution infrastructure, as well as subsidies and other forms of support for the electricity sector.

This data as obtained from NBS, is measured by looking at the annual government capital expenditure on electricity (in billions of naira)

3.4. Nature and Sources of Data

To empirically investigate and provide substantial answers to the present study's research questions, the researcher used secondary data sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics covering a period of 33 years, i.e. 1990 – 2022. Secondary data was used for this study because it is considered to be the most appropriate method for the needed information, and it also has added advantages over other methods. Additionally, it saves time and is more cost-effective.

3.5. Pre-Estimation Techniques and Estimation Procedures

The study employs four methods of data analysis. First, descriptive statistics is used to examine the trend and magnitude of the selected variables. Secondly, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) is the pre-co-integration test. It is used to determine the order of integration of a variable, that is, how many times it has to be differenced or not to become stationary. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test is used because of its superiority over the Dickey-Fuller (DF) Test. In the ADF test, the more negative it is, the stronger the rejection of the Hypothesis that there is a unit root at some level of confidence

Third, the Johansen Co-integration test checks whether the regression residuals are co-integrated, that is, to test whether there is a long-run relationship between dependent and independent variables in the model (Ogundipe and Alege, 2013). Cointegration is a means for correctly testing hypotheses concerning the relationship between variables having unit roots of order one.

The Johansen co-integration equation used in the study is a multivariate model designed to test the long-run equilibrium relationship between time series variables. Based on the study, the equation is applied to evaluate the relationship between electricity supply (ELEC) and industrial productivity (IND), along with other relevant explanatory variables. The general Johansen co-integration model is stated as:

$$\Delta Y_t = \Pi Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \mu + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

- Y_t = Vector of non-stationary variables
- Δ = First difference operator
- Π = Coefficient matrix that contains information about the long-run relationships among the variables
- Γ_i = Short-run dynamic coefficients
- μ = Constant term
- ε_t = White noise error term
- k = Lag length

The final stage is the Vector Error Correction (VECM) test. It serves as the dynamic system reconciling the static long-run equilibrium relationship of the co-integrated time series with its short-run dynamics. The E-views 12 student version software is used to carry out these tests.

The Johansen test transforms the VAR model into the VECM by using first differences of the time series:

$$\Delta Y_t = B d_{t-1} + \Pi Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \mu$$

Where:

- ΔY_t = the first differences of Y_t
- $B d_t$ = deterministic terms (constant and trend)
- ΠY_{t-1} = the long-term equilibrium relationships (cointegration)
- Γ_i = Short-run dynamic coefficients
- μ = White noise error term

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS OF RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The chapter presents the results of the secondary data analysis in the research and a comprehensive interpretation of the findings, aiming to answer the research questions. The data series for each of the research variables is: the Industrial productivity index (IND, dependent variable), and the independent variables are Electricity supply (ELEC), Installed Capacity (INCA), and Government Expenditure on Electricity infrastructures (GEXP) were obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics from the year 1990-2022 (see appendix). This chapter is, therefore, divided into subsections. The first is the descriptive results which were done to enable the researcher to observe the nature and structure of the research data; Then, the overtime movement of the variable data using trend analysis; additionally, the unit root test for checking the stationarity of the research data is also presented in one of the sections; following the unit root result, the study adopted the Johansen cointegration and Vector Error Correction model test to determine the relationship and impact between the research variables.

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics of Data

Table 4.1: Variables Descriptive Statistics

	IND	ELEC	INCA	GEXP
Mean	4.9470	17.0816	8.7205	6.094
Median	4.9398	17.1665	8.7718	5.5544

Maximum	5.2325	17.4906	9.0442	10.6133
Minimum	4.4909	16.5006	8.4224	0.9933
Std. Dev.	0.2122	0.2810	0.2114	2.6951
Skewness	-0.6753	-0.5269	-0.3826	0.1447
Kurtosis	2.9394	2.1413	1.6858	1.8910
Jargue-Bera	2.4370	2.4638	3.0835	1.7252
Probability	0.2957	0.2917	0.2140	0.4221
Sum	158.3037	546.6118	279.0546	195.0047
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.3965	2.4485	1.3849	225.1640
Observations	32	32	32	32

Source: Author's Output from EViews

Table 4.1 above presents the summary descriptive data for each research variable, such as the Industrial Productivity Index (IND, dependent variable). The independent variables are Electricity supply (ELEC), Installed Capacity (INCA), and Government Expenditure on Electricity infrastructures (GEXP). Therefore, Table 4.1 presents the summary statistics of the logged values of these four variables.

The mean values, which depict the average value of the data series, are obtained by summing the series values divided by the number. Thus, as presented in the above table, the mean for Industrial

Productivity Index (IND), Electricity supply (ELEC), Installed Capacity (INCA), and Government Expenditure (GEXP) are 4.946991, 17.08162, 8.720456, and 6.093897, respectively. The ELEC variable has the highest value, implying that over time, the electricity supply has increased. Meanwhile, IND, INCA, and GEXP have been relatively low compared to the ELEC mean, with the Industrial Productivity Index having the lowest mean.

For the median values, we have 4.939837, 17.08162, 8.720456, and 6.093897 for LnIND, LnELEC, LnINCA, and LGEXP, respectively. The interpretation here is similar to that of all the variables' mean values. The Industrial Productivity Index (IND) had the highest middle value, followed by installed capacity (INCA), and Government expenditure on electrical infrastructures (GEXP)

Similarly, the maximum and minimum numbers were highest for the industrial productivity Index (IND). As observed from Table 4.1 the Maximum and Minimum numbers are 5.232498 and 4.490881, 17.49058 and 16.50059, 9.044227 and 8.422443, and 4.10.61325 and 0.993252 for the logged values of industrial productivity (LnIND), Electricity supply (LnELEC), installed capacity (LnINCA) and Government expenditure on electrical infrastructures (LnGEXP) each in order.

The spread of dispersion of the data series from their means is expressed by their standard deviation. The above shows that the mean for IND is 4.946991, and the standard deviation is 0.212243. Given these values, there is a considerable close variation for IND. For the mean values of ELEC (17.08162), INCA (8.720456), and GEXP (6.093897), we observed that the standard deviations of these variables are clustered closely around the mean given that they are very small.

We have 0.281038, 0.211366, and 0.2695061 for the standard deviation of INCA, GEXP, and GEXP respectively.

Furthermore, Table 4.1 displays the coefficients for Kurtosis and Skewness. These statistics provide information on the height and spread of a distribution in a data series. Skewness measures the degree to which the data is spread out, while Kurtosis measures the peakiness or flatness of the distribution. If the Kurtosis coefficient exceeds 3, the data series is considered peaked or has a heavier tail than a normal distribution. Conversely, if the Kurtosis value is below 3, it is regarded as platykurtic or flat compared to a normal distribution. A Skewness coefficient of zero indicates a normal distribution. A positive Skewness value suggests the existence of a long right-tail distribution, while a negative value implies a long left-tailed distribution in the data series

From Table 4.1, we can observe that IND (-0.675289), ELEC (-0.526902), and INCA (-0.382584) all have negative skewness, implying that they have long left tails. While GEXP (0.144748) have a positive skewness value, which means the variable has a right-tailed distribution. For the kurtosis measures, all the variables under examination are below the threshold of 3: variables IND (2.939387), ELEC (2.141310), INCA (2.1685787), and GEXP (1.899956), which is an indication that they are platykurtic, which means that they have thinner tails than a normal distribution.

The Jarque Berra Statistics is a test used to confirm the normality of data series. The null hypothesis states that the data series is normally distributed at a 5% statistical significance level. Implies that samples from a normal distribution have an expected skewness of zero and an expected excess kurtosis of 3. However, from the table above once again, we observe that the Jarque-Berra values for the logged values of Industrial productivity index (LnIND), Electricity supply (LnELEC),

Installed Capacity (LnINCA), and Government expenditure (LnGXP) are 2.436980, 2.463801, 3.083519, and 1.725206 respectively and all their p-values are greater than 0.05. Therefore, in the present research model, we fail to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that the data series are not normally distributed. This interpretation is in line with the skewness and kurtosis results obtained in which the skewness values of all variables are non-zero and their kurtosis values do not exactly equal 3.

4.1.2 Unit Root Test

The result of the stationarity test of the research data series was tested by performing a unit root test. Before performing the stationarity of the dataset, a Log transformation was performed on each variable's data series. This put the data on a more comparable scale, helped normalise the distribution of the variables, and stabilised the variance of a time series, making it more suitable for statistical analysis. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approach was adopted, and the results are shown in Table 4.2. This test is generally accepted as a measure of the unit root. More specifically, the null hypothesis of the state states that a time series of data has a unity root, i.e., no stationarity; on the other hand, the alternate hypothesis states that a data set does not have a unit root.

Table 4.2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Stationarity Test Results

Variables	ADF-Stat.	t-Stat. (5%)	Prob	Integration Order	Stationary at?
IND	-4.018855	-2.963972	0.0042	I(1)	1 st difference
ELEC	-5.612610	-2.963972	0.0001	I(1)	1 st difference
INCA	-4.051083	-2.963972	0.0039	I(2)	2 nd difference

GEXP	-6.087705	-2.963972	0.0000	I(1)	1 st difference
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Source: Eviews Output by Author

The ADF results in Table 4.2 show that the variables in the first model ($IND = f(ELEC)$), are both stationary at 1st difference that is, the dependent variable (IND) and the independent variables, such as ELEC, at 5% significance levels are both being interpreted as being integrated at order one I(1). This implies that the data sets of these independent variables have to be differenced once to attain stationarity, which was done at a 5% significance level. Therefore, the Vector error correction model becomes the appropriate research model estimation method for this study. However, the second model ($ELEC = f(INCA, GEXP)$) IN Table 4.2 is seen to have a mixed order of stationary variables. While ELEC and GEXP are stationary at the first difference, INCA is stationary at the second difference. Hence, for the second model, the Auto-regressive distributive lag model becomes the most appropriate for estimating the second model. It will be used to examine the long-run and short-run relationships between variables

4.1.3 Trend Analysis

As the name implies, trend analysis is used to identify trends, patterns, or changes in a data series over time. It examines historical data like this present research to comprehend its direction of movement over time. Below is an overview of the trend analysis of each of the research variables.

Figure 4.1: Variables Trend Analysis
Source: Author's Output from Eviews

4.1.3.1. ELEC Trend Analysis

The overall trend of electricity supply in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022 reveals periods of stability, decline, and recovery. The early 1990s saw stable production levels, followed by notable declines in the late 1990s and early 2000s. The mid-2000s to early 2010s experienced fluctuations, with minor recoveries. The period from 2016 to 2022 shows stabilisation and a slight growth trend, indicating improved conditions and efforts to enhance Electricity supply capabilities; this indicates an overall increase in Nigeria's capacity to produce electricity. However, the trend isn't perfectly linear. There are noticeable fluctuations in the data that can be attributed to fuel price fluctuations, amongst others. As a major oil producer, global oil price movements might influence Nigeria's

Electricity supply costs. Overall, Industrial productivity moved somewhat in tandem with electricity supply, suggesting a positive association. Periods of improved electricity generation often aligned with growth in industrial output, reinforcing the dependency of industrial processes on stable power supply.

Figure4.2: ELEC Trend Analysis
Source: Author’s Output from Eviews

4.1.3.2 INCA Trend Analysis

According to the installed capacity trend analysis figure, the installed capacity of Nigeria's electricity sector from 1990 to 2022 provides insight into the country's potential for electricity production over three decades. This analysis identifies key periods of stability, growth, and minor fluctuations. Suggesting that there were efforts to improve and expand the electricity infrastructure; however, significant long-term growth was limited, and the sector faced periods of stagnation and minor decline. This reflects the broader challenges in the Nigerian electricity sector, including investment needs, infrastructure maintenance, and policy implementation. The most

striking feature is the stagnation in installed capacity for most of the analyzed period (1990-2022). This limited growth suggests that the expansion of power generation infrastructure in Nigeria hasn't kept pace with the potential demand for electricity. This could contribute to the country's persistent challenges with power shortages and blackouts.

Although installed capacity increased, its impact on industrial productivity was not immediately evident in all periods due to poor capacity utilization. Nonetheless, the long-run positive relationship indicates that over time, increased capacity supports industrial output when efficiently used.

Figure 4.3: INCA Trend Analysis
Source: Author's Output from Eviews

4.1.3.3. GEXP Trend Analysis

Figure 4.4 below shows the trend analysis of government expenditure on electricity infrastructure (GEXP) in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022. Unlike the previous trend analysis, we observe two distinct

phases in government spending on electricity infrastructure here. The period 1990 to 2007 can be said to be the phase of gradual increase, as a gradual upward trend in government spending is seen on the line chart, possibly driven by growing demand or an acknowledgement of existing infrastructure limitations. Then, the period from 2008 to 2022 was characterised by a sharp drop in spending, which has lingered up to this time. However, the factors responsible for this drop are unclear from the trend. However, suggestively, the year 2008 also coincided with the global financial crisis; further in the period, the country also witnessed a shift in government spending, and the power sector became privatised in 2013. Whatever the case, the fluctuating spending pattern in the later phase suggests a lack of a consistent long-term strategy for infrastructure development in the electricity sector. An inconsistency that can hinder progress in addressing the country's power challenges. The trend analysis revealed a weak impact of GEXP on electricity supply, and consequently on industrial productivity. This implies that while public spending exists, delays in execution or corruption might dampen its effectiveness in driving industrial growth.

Figure 4.4: GEXP Trend Analysis
Source: Author's Output from Eviews

4.1.3.4. DPIN Trend Analysis

Figure 4.5 shows the industrial productivity index (IND) trend analysis. The graph shows a general upward trend in industrial productivity, which characterised the period under study. However, there were still periods of fluctuation despite the overall positive trend. These fluctuations are observed in the index around 1995, 2000, and 2010. These dips could be attributed to various factors. For example, the dip after the year 2005 coincided with the global financial crisis, which most likely affected production levels and productivity. However, we observed a recovery phase from 2015, which suggests that the industrial sector started stabilising and recovering from the previous decline, possibly due to corrective measures or improved economic conditions.

Figure 4.5: IND Trend Analysis

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

4.2 Data Analysis and The Results

4.2.1 Model 1 OLS Regression

Table 4.3: OLS Regression

Dependent Variable: D(ELEC)

Method: Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0316	0.0521	0.6057	0.5494
DD(INCA)	1.3227	0.4992	2.6492	0.0129
D(GEXP)	0.0019	0.034	0.0554	0.9562

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

The OLS regression analysis findings show that the installed capacity factor and Government expenditure on electricity generated are statistically significant. However, only INCA is statistically significant, indicating that a unit increase in this variable will bring about a more significant than the one-unit increase in electricity generated. This suggests that in the short run, electricity supply and other independent variables are interconnected to enhanced productivity within Nigeria's industrial sector.

4.2.2 Model 1: Lag Selection Results

Table 4.4: Lag selection Results for Model 1 and Model 2

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous Variable: D(ELEC)

Number of Obs.: 31

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC.	HQ
0	-18.8428	NA	0.0132	1.344697	1.4372	1.3749
1	10.8655	53.6667*	0.0025*	-0.3139*	-0.0364*	-0.2234*
2	12.3937	2.5634	0.0030	-0.1544	0.3081	-0.0036

**Indicates lag order selected by the criterion*

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

To avoid the loss of degrees of freedom, the optional lag for the two-research model analysis was chosen following the lag selection result presented in Table 4.4 above. The result shows that the test satisfies one lag based on LR, FPE, AIC SC, and HQ. Therefore, the two research models would be further estimated using 1 lag.

4.2.3 Cointegration Test

Determining the level of stationarity of the variables set the pace for co-integration using the Johansen Cointegration test. The co-integration test is used to check for long run relationship between the dependent and independent variables (Ogundipe and Amaghionyeodiwe, 2013). The

co-integration test was carried out using the Johansen technique also using Eviews software package, and it produced the following results:

Table 4.5: Johansen Co-integration Test Result

Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistics	Critical Value	Prob **	Max-Eigen Statistic	Critical Value	Prob. Value
None *	0.514988	27.96588	25.87211	0.0271	22.43100	19.38704	0.0175
At most 1	0.163513	5.534875	12.51798	0.5215	5.534875	12.51798	0.5215

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

*** denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level**

****MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values**

Log-likelihood -1056.999

Normalised cointegrating coefficients = IND – 0.691332ELEC

Standard error = (0.09233)

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

From the Johansen table above, the Trace Statistics and the Maximum Eigenvalue, as well as their critical values, indicate one cointegrating equation or relationship at the 0.05 significance level. The trace Statistics (27.96588) and Max-Eigen statistic (22.43100) are greater than their corresponding critical values (25.87211 and 19.38704), respectively. Therefore, it is deduced that a long-run relationship exists between the dependent variable, IND and the independent variable, ELEC. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis of no co-integrating equations.

Furthermore, in interpreting the normalized co-integrating equation in the long run, we reverse the coefficient signs of the Johansen normalized coefficients, indicating that the direction of one variable changes in response to a unit change in another variable. IND is the target variable, and

we observe that Electricity supply (ELEC) maintained a significant long-term positive relationship with the industrial productivity index (IND). More specifically, the equation revealed that a unit increase in ELEC will lead to an increase in IND to the tune of about 69.13

Table 4.6: The Johansen Long Run Result

Normalise Cointegrating Equation	
IND	ELEC
1.0000000	-0.691332 (0.09233)

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

4.2.4 Vector Error Correction Model

The presence of a long-run relationship among the research variables, as established by the Johansen cointegration, led to the application of the vector error correction model (VECM). This method is, therefore, considered the best option for further analysis to correct disequilibrium caused in the short run. This method is adopted to determine the speed of adjustment of the disequilibrium in the long-run relationship in the short-run. In other words, the Error correction vector estimates give us the speed of adjustment within which the model will return to equilibrium following any disturbances.

Table 4.7: Vector Error Correction Model

Error Correction:	D(IND)	D(ELEC)
CointEq1	-0.3604 (0.2046)	0.4055 (0.3922)

	[-1.7613]	[1.0338]
D(IND(-1))	0.4384	0.2410
	(0.2851)	(0.5464)
	[1.5381]	[0.4411]
D(ELEC(-1))	-0.0343	-0.1960
	(0.1073)	(0.2057)
	[-0.3197]	[-0.9530]
C	-0.0155	0.0430
	(0.0311)	(0.0596)
	[-0.5000]	[0.7221]

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

Table 4.6 above shows the VECM report from the analysis. The coefficients on the lagged differenced variables represent the short-run dynamics of the system. They capture the immediate impact of changes in one variable on the others. In this table, it is seen that the disequilibrium in the long run can be corrected with speed in the short run, thereby adjusting the value of industrial productivity to equilibrium. The report indicates that about 36% of the disequilibrium in the long run is corrected in the short run. However, the coefficient of ECT with the lag Electricity supply (ELEC) is negative but not significant in the short run; similarly, the lag of industrial productivity is positive and insignificant; this implies the lack of significant adjustments towards long-run equilibrium in any disequilibrium situation. However, the lagged dependent variable has a positive

feedback impact on itself in the short run, which is also desirable for validating the Genuity of the equations estimated.

4.2.5 Residual Diagnostic Test

Table 4.8: OLS Diagnostic Tests

Types	Checks	Statistics/P-value	Conclusion
Durbin Waston	Autocorrection	2.267222	No Autocorrelation
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	Heteroscedasticity	0.009819/0.9902	No Heteroscedasticity
Breusch-Godfrey	Serial Correlation	0.382562/0.6858	No Serial Correlation
F-statistics	Model Significance	3.54658/0.042293	Significant model

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

Table 4.8 presents the results of the diagnostic checks conducted to validate the reliability of the OLS regression results. The tests include the Durbin Waston statistics test for Autocorrelation, the Breusch-Godfrey Test for Serial correlation, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test for Heteroskedasticity, and the F-statistics test, which checks for the overall model significance. The F-stats and probabilities of Breusch show positivity as they all suggest rejecting the null hypothesis for each category of diagnostic tests. While, the Durbin Waston statistics fall within the acceptable range ($1.5 < 2.3 < 2.5$), and the F-statistics p-value is less than 0.05 level, thus depicting overall model significance.

The diagnostic tests of the VECM model are essential for ensuring adequacy and that the model's results and deductible conclusions are reliable and accurate to reliability and accuracy.

Table 4.9: VECM Diagnostic Tests

Types	Checks	Statistics	P-value	Conclusion
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	Heteroscedasticity	12.74748	0.8064	No Autocorrelation
Breusch-Godfrey	Serial Correlation	0.454918	0.7683	No Heteroscedasticity
Portmanteau	Autocorrelation	2.223647	0.8825	No Serial Correlation
F-statistics	Model Significance	13.62058	0.000012	Significant model

Source: Author's Output from Eviews

The VECM autocorrelation residual test report presented in Table 4.9 above shows that up to 4 lags of residuals have no autocorrelation, as their p-values are greater than 0.05. Hence, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the model has no autocorrelation.

The LM serial correlation test method also supports the conclusion that no correlation exists. In Table 4.9, we see that the hypothesis that there is no serial correlation in the research model is supported as the p-values for the maximum lag length criteria used for the analysis are all greater than the rejection threshold of 0.05. Hence, we again conclude that the model has no serial correlation at lag 2.

Furthermore, the diagnostic test for heteroscedasticity in Table 4.9 above shows that the research residual is not heteroskedastic. This is deduced from the observed p-value, which is greater than 0.05.

Lastly, the F-statistics show a p-value of less than 0,05, so it is concluded that the overall model specification is statistically significant.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Following the analysis of the first model ($ELEC=f(INCA, GEXP)$), the OLS regression results obtained showed that the a priori expectations of the research variables (INCA and GEXP) were aligned with the findings. Thus, installed capacity (INCA) and government expenditure on electricity facilities (GEXP) exerted a positive impact on Electricity Generation (ELEC). However, only the effect of INCA is seen to be statistically significant. This demonstrates a related effect of power plant capacity factors on determining the level of electricity supplied. Furthermore, the second model, VECM estimation, revealed a long-run relationship between the industrial productivity index (IND) and electricity generation (ELEC). This long-run implication of this study corresponds with the findings from Adewale and Afolabi (2021), whose study highlighted that a stable and uninterrupted electricity supply plays a very important role in enhancing a country's industrial performance level. Bassey et al. (2022) also revealed that irregular electricity supply could weaken the industrial performance in Nigeria and recommended a well-rounded energy mix to complement existing energy sources. Additionally, Abraham (2015) and Olayemi (2012) both found that electricity supply had a significant impact on manufacturing productivity, with Abraham emphasising the need for prudent use of infrastructure funds and Olayemi suggesting the initiation of independent power projects. However, Orji (2017) found that while electricity consumption positively impacted industrial sector performance, gross capital formation and government spending had a negative impact. Nwajinka et al. (2013) also highlighted the need for sustained funding and private partnerships in the power sector to enhance economic growth.

Furthermore, the research hypothesis is evaluated using the OLS regression, cointegration, and VECM analysis results. The first null hypothesis, which states that Electricity supply has no

significant impact on industrial productivity in Nigeria, is to be rejected. This is because the interpreted result of the ELEC variable is seen to have a significant long-term impact on industrial productivity (IND) with a cointegrating coefficient of 0.691332. This implies that a unit increase in ELEC will cause a 69.137% increase in IND. Hence, the alternate hypothesis is accepted. These findings align with the investigation result of Ijuo et al. (2015). As the scholars also discovered, electricity generated and supplied positively impacts the productivity of manufacturing industries.

Similarly, we fail to accept the second hypothesis, stating that there is no significant long-run relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria. This is because the Trace statistic and Maxi-Eigen statistics of the Johansen Cointegration result in Table 4.5 show that there is, in fact, one cointegrating equation in which the ELEC variable is observed to have a long-run relationship with the dependent variable, IND, in Nigeria. Vhi et al. (2017) also obtained similar results investigating the relationship between electricity and manufacturing output. The authors' findings revealed that instability in power supply negatively affects manufacturing efficiency and industrial output. Hence, they concluded that stable electricity consumption is important for Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Chiazoka et al. (2013) also revealed a long-run relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity in Nigeria.

Regarding the third hypothesis, "Capacity utilisation does not significantly affect electricity supply in Nigeria", the OLS regression result equation in Table 4.3 shows that the capacity variable significantly impacts electricity supply, ELEC. The capacity variable was also observed to have the most impact on ELEC, implying that in the power sector, the capacity of plants and other generating equipment plays a great role in the model. Akiri, Odike and Peace's (2015) study revealed that capacity utilization plays a significant role in the relationship between electricity

supply and industrial productivity. The International Energy Agency (IEA) study also corresponds with these research findings concerning the important role of generation capacity utilisation in increasing industrial production.

Lastly, we also fail to reject the fourth hypothesis, which states that government expenditure on power has no significant impact on industrial productivity, given that Table 4.5 results revealed that government expenditure on power exerts positive but insignificantly on ELEC in the long run. The GEXP variable is observed to have the least effect on ELEC in the research model. This result, therefore, contrasts the investigative findings of Edafe (2014), whose study on public expenditure on electricity shows that while recurrent expenditure positively impacts electricity generation, capital expenditure shows a negative impact. However, several studies have highlighted the need for improved electricity supply, efficient allocation of government expenditure, and addressing corruption in the power sector to promote growth and sustainable development (Edafe, 2014; Akiri, Odike & Peace, 2015).

4.4 Policy Implications of Findings

The socio-economic policy implication of the major findings of this present research analysis is expressed as follows:

Firstly, it has been deduced that electricity supply positively impacts industrial productivity in Nigeria; however, its lagged value negatively impacts industrial productivity in the short-run due to inadequate supply/epileptic power supply and misallocation of funds. The economic intuition behind this is that its long-run direct impact aligns with the priori expectation, which is expressed that an increase in power supply increases industrial productivity, which in turn enhances

economic growth, as postulated in the neoclassical theory of growth. In this theory, it is discussed that investments in new technologies, such as renewable energy sources or more efficient power generation methods, can impact the overall growth of an economy through an increase in industrial productivity, thus providing the framework for comprehending the relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity in this present study . Therefore, this finding implies that electricity supply can be an effective tool for government, policymakers and industry stakeholders to use in addressing the prevailing crisis facing Nigeria manufacturing organizations in staying afloat, most especially in this period of persistent inflation and fuel price hikes resulting from the removal of subsidy amongst other factors.

The findings about electricity generation capacity exerting a positive impact on electricity generation implicate that installing higher capacity in electrical plants to increase power generation yields positive results in the short run. This, in turn, improves industrial productivity in the long run and can also be a great tool in improving power stability in the country.

Furthermore, government expenditure on capital projects concerning electricity generation was also found to have a very small positive effect on electricity generation, although not statistically significant; however, according to a priori expectation deduced from the intervention theory about public finance which advocates for intervention policies from the government through investment in education, research and even infrastructure development. This theory and that of Keynes's "General Theory", which supports government intervention during economic turmoil as it is our present society, holds that government can boost demand and correct market failures by spending much cash. Hence, it provided insights into the a priori expectation of the GEXP variable (see section 2.2). Therefore, government expenditure on power is expected to improve power supply,

which in turn can enhance the productivity of the industrial section in Nigeria. Nevertheless, because of misallocation of funds, corruption and lack of monitoring and evaluation of projects, amongst other factors, this was not the case in the findings of GEXP, highlighting the need for reforms in capital budgeting and implementation.

However, as with any research model specification, this present study's model represents real-world problems and could fall short of fully capturing the complexities facing Nigeria, which differs with time and political administrations. Hence, the impact of these variables investigated may not be as direct as the results indicated in improving electricity supply and industrial productivity. In the actual complex instances, as we have in Nigeria presently, power instability has been an industry for ages, which has resulted in firms adopting generation plants and solar systems. Thus, improving the power supply may cause unemployment in these alternative market supplies, which may also impact the service and productivity of the energy industrial chain. Therefore, the government must seek strategic ways to balance policies in such a way that no sector of the manufacturing or service industry is left worse off.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

In this study, the researcher empirically investigated the impact of electricity generation on industrial productivity in Nigeria, employing data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) spanning from 1990 to 2022. Two models were specified using electricity supply (ELEC), installed capacity (INCA), and government expenditure on power (GEXP). Here, the researcher tests for the possible impact of INCA and GEXP on electricity to find traces of their indirect effects on industrial productivity. Further, the second model had the industrial productivity index as the dependent variable and ELEC as the independent variable to check for a direct relationship between both variables. In analysing the obtained data series, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test was used to test for the stationarity of the time series variables. The result from this test revealed both the dependent and independent variables to be stationary at first differencing (I (1)).

Furthermore, the study used Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to identify the long-run cointegration relationships among the variables in the research second model and capture the short-run dynamic relationship interactions. While the first model variable was differenced and Ordinary Least Square was used in the model estimation. The result from the cointegration test through the Johansen approach showed that there is one cointegrating equation in the research model. This implies that a long-run relationship exists between ELEC and IND. Based on the sequential modified LR test statistic, Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC) and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ), which

recommended the one-lag selection, the vector error correction test was run. Findings from this analysis revealed that ELEC has a long-term positive impact on industrial productivity in Nigeria. Implying that an increase in ELEC will increase the industrial productivity index. Similarly, INCA exerted the most impact in the first model on ELEC, and GEXP's impact was the least and non-significant.

Four hypotheses were tested, and three were rejected. Summarily, the significant findings concerning the hypotheses tested in the course of this study are:

Electricity supply (ELEC) was found to positively impact industrial productivity in Nigeria, which was also statistically significant. Therefore, we accepted the alternate hypothesis which states that ELEC significantly impact industrial productivity

Additionally, ELEC was seen to have a long-term positive relationship with industrial productivity, which was also statistically significant. There we failed to accept the null hypothesis and stated that ELEC have a significant long relationship with IND

Installed capacity (INCA) was also observed to improve electricity supply in Nigeria, and this finding is statistically significant. Hence, we rejected the null hypothesis.

Government expenditure on power infrastructure was also found to impact electricity supply, but the impact was not statistically significant; hence, we failed to reject the hypothesis and concluded that GEXP has no significant impact on electricity generation.

For the analysis of disequilibrium caused by the short-run dynamics, the report indicates that about 36% of the disequilibrium in the long run is corrected in the short run. However, the coefficient of

ECT with the lag of industrial productivity (IND) is positive but not significant in the short run, and that of ELEC is negative and insignificant in the short run; this implies the lack of significant adjustments towards long-run equilibrium in any disequilibrium. However, the dependent variable has a feedback impact on itself in the short run, which is also desirable for validating the Genuity of the equations estimated. Finally, the post-estimation diagnostic tests for both research models revealed that the OLS residual estimates and the VECM model's residual estimate were free of auto-correlation, serial correction, and heteroscedasticity. Further, the F-statistics of both models showed overall model significance for both research models.

5.2 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of electricity generation on industrial productivity. Although studies have shown that a stable power supply enhances industrial productivity and stimulates the economy, Nigeria is faced with prolonged power instability, forcing industries to seek alternatives whose costs weigh heavily. There were also literary works which found no significant relationship between electricity supply and industrial productivity. A range of studies have explored the impact of electricity generation on Nigeria's industrial productivity. Abraham (2015) and Olayemi (2012) both found a positive correlation, with Abraham emphasising the need for prudent use of funds and deregulation of the power sector and Olayemi suggesting the initiation of independent power projects. However, Nwajinka (2013) and Elekwa (2016) presented contrasting views, with Nwajinka finding no significant impact and Elekwa identifying a negative impact. These studies collectively highlight the complex and multifaceted nature of the relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity in Nigeria.

However, the OLS regression model findings showed INCA's high-magnitude impact on ELEC. This impact was positive and statistically significant, while ELEC was not. Johansen cointegration for this present study shows a long-run relationship between industrial productivity (IND) and electricity supply (ELEC); the VECM analysis concludes that 36% of the disequilibrium in the long run is corrected in the short run. Another conclusion arrived at is from the normalised cointegrating coefficient. From this equation, the study deduced that electricity supply (ELEC) positively impacts Nigeria's industrial productivity (IND). In light of these findings, this study's four postulated hypotheses were evaluated, and three were rejected as no statistical evidence supported the null hypotheses.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the research findings, Nigeria can significantly enhance its industrial productivity through improved electricity generation and supply, fostering economic growth and development by implementing the following recommendations.

- i. **Strategic capital expenditure budgeting towards the power sector:** Given the limited effectiveness of government spending on power infrastructure on electricity generation, which stems from factors such as misallocation of funds, corruption, and various challenges throughout the budgeting and implementation processes, the government should consider establishing a proactive monitoring and evaluation committee. This committee would oversee capital expenditures and deliver quarterly reports, particularly focused on the routine maintenance and enhancements of electricity grid infrastructure, transmission lines, and distribution networks. Such

- measures would promote greater transparency concerning the allocation and utilization of these funds.
- ii. **Enhance Installed Capacity:** The installed capacity exerts the most impact on electricity supply. Hence, the government, through the Federal Ministry of Power and National Integrated Power Project (NIPP) initiative, together with other non-governmental stakeholders in the power sector, needs to direct more efforts into increasing the installed capacity of power generation to increase the supply of power needed to meet industries' growing demand. This can be achieved by constructing new power plants and upgrading existing ones.
 - iii. **Increase Power Supply through Renewable Energy Sources:** Since power supply was found to exert a positive impact on industrial productivity. The Tinubu-led administration's Electricity Act of 2023, which intends to incorporate renewable energy sources into Nigeria's energy mix, should be meticulously monitored and evaluated. This will help the nation reduce its dependency on fossil fuels and increase its power supply. While promoting the development and utilisation of renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power, incentives and subsidies can be provided to support renewable energy projects.
 - iv. **Enhance Policy Coordination and Implementation:** Effective coordination between different government ministries and agencies, such as the Federal Ministry of Power and Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading (NBET), the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), and the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), etc., involved in the power sector, is crucial. A coherent and integrated approach to policy implementation can

ensure the success of initiatives such as the Electricity Act of 2023 to improve electricity supply and industrial productivity.

5.4 Contributions to Knowledge

This study's investigation into the impact of electricity generation on industrial productivity contributes greatly to the plethora of academic and non-academic research on increasing industrial productivity by employing the latest and historical data of interest to update findings that are more reflective of the prevailing challenges and opportunities that face both the power and industrial sectors in Nigeria. More specifically, the study contributed to existing knowledge by:

- i. Highlighting the role of capacity utilisation of electrical plants proxied by an installed capacity variable, which measured the ratio of the actual electricity generated by a power plant to its maximum potential electricity generation capacity over a specific period, usually a year. This was one of the major findings of this research, which shows that the capacity factor exerts the most impact on electricity generation/supply.
- ii. Examining government intervention's role in capital expenditure on electricity infrastructure in the country. The study concluded that government expenditure on power can become significant if certain factors, such as corruption and misallocation of resources, are checked strategically.
- iii. Providing a literature background on the different sources of energy that serve as alternatives to industries and a theoretical foundation for establishing an a priori expectation on the direction of the relationship between electricity supply, installed capacity, government expenditure on power, and industrial productivity.

At its core, the research offered well-founded insight into the intricate relationship between electricity generation and industrial productivity within the Nigerian context by examining the electricity supply, capacity factor of plants, and government expenditure directed at the country's power sector.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

One of the limitations of this research is the time constraints faced by the researcher, who had to balance coursework, employment, and thesis completion. Another limitation is the challenge of obtaining data from open sources online. Even with the help of NBS, the researcher could only access consistent data from 1990 to 2022. While reviewing the relevant literature, the researcher encountered difficulties accessing journals with the necessary materials. Some websites were secure and inaccessible, while others required subscriptions to access the required materials. Additionally, the researcher encountered challenges in navigating the procedures of the suitable econometric estimator for the research model.

5.6 Suggestions for Future Studies

To improve on this study, future research could conduct a more comprehensive analysis of electricity generation and industrial impact by capturing prevailing data. Additionally, further research could explore the potential role of other energy sources, such as solar and fossil fuels, in driving industrial productivity in Nigeria.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: Research Raw Data

Electricity Generation Impact on Industrial Productivity 1990-2022				
Measure	Industrial Production	Installed capacity	Electricity Generation	Govt. Expenditure on electricity
Year	Index	Mega Watts	Mega Watt	N'Million
1990	130.6	4548.0	1536.9	451.7
1991	138.8	4548.0	1517.2	478.7
1992	136.2	4580.0	1656.4	1166.7
1993	131.7	4548.0	1658.8	1317.4
1994	129.2	4548.0	1772.4	1494.2
1995	128.8	4548.0	1658.4	1739.5
1996	132.5	4548.0	1854.2	2215.9
1997	140.6	4548.0	1839.8	3187.8
1998	133.9	4548.0	1724.9	5200.3
1999	129.1	5580.0	1858.8	8685.5
2000	138.9	5580.0	1738.3	11102.4
2001	144.1	6180.0	1689.9	12135.1
2002	145.2	6108.0	2337.3	26428.8
2003	147.0	6130.0	6180.0	26138.8
2004	151.2	6240.4	2763.6	31883.2
2005	158.8	6656.4	2779.3	40670.2
2006	151.5	7,440.20	2795	45.1
2007	89.2	7,959.90	2810.7	49.6
2008	91.2	8469.5	2826.4	104.5
2009	92.4	7644	2842.1	124.9
2010	92.1	6423	1,606	119.0
2011	117.74	6477	2,054.10	94.9
2012	133.7	6531	2,274	138.4
2013	162.85	6585	4,214	23.4
2014	186.85	7214	6,154	147.8
2015	187.26	7433	6,616	7.2
2016	176.08	7245	7,184	2.7
2017	175.72	7198	6,995	50.3
2018	179.39	7483	7,384	27.9
2019	180.37	7521	7,381	30.2
2020	182.03	7559	8,083	32.5

2021	183.68	7597	8,785	34.8
2022	93.80	4,747	4,443.1	35.4

Source: NBS

Appendix II: Unit root test of Research variables

Null Hypothesis: ELEC has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.621226	0.4605
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.653730	
5% level	-2.957110	
10% level	-2.617434	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(ELEC)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:57
Sample (adjusted): 1991 2022
Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ELEC(-1)	-0.147367	0.090899	-1.621226	0.1154
C	1.210482	0.728240	1.662201	0.1069
R-squared	0.080555	Mean dependent var	0.033175	
Adjusted R-squared	0.049907	S.D. dependent var	0.317432	
S.E. of regression	0.309409	Akaike info criterion	0.552158	
Sum squared resid	2.872024	Schwarz criterion	0.643767	
Log likelihood	-6.834533	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.582524	
F-statistic	2.628374	Durbin-Watson stat	1.985781	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.115434			

Null Hypothesis: INCA has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.528948	0.5064
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.653730	
5% level	-2.957110	
10% level	-2.617434	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(INCA)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:59
Sample (adjusted): 1991 2022
Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INCA(-1)	-0.135426	0.088575	-1.528948	0.1368
C	1.182316	0.772632	1.530245	0.1364
R-squared	0.072290	Mean dependent var	0.001338	
Adjusted R-squared	0.041366	S.D. dependent var	0.106463	
S.E. of regression	0.104238	Akaike info criterion	-1.623824	
Sum squared resid	0.325965	Schwarz criterion	-1.532215	
Log likelihood	27.98118	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.593458	
F-statistic	2.337681	Durbin-Watson stat	1.220403	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.136754			

Null Hypothesis: D(ELEC) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.733455	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.661661	
5% level	-2.960411	
10% level	-2.619160	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(ELEC,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:58
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022
Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(ELEC(-1))	-1.155617	0.201557	-5.733455	0.0000
C	0.043412	0.059420	0.730604	0.4709
R-squared	0.531294	Mean dependent var	-0.021574	
Adjusted R-squared	0.515132	S.D. dependent var	0.466391	
S.E. of regression	0.324759	Akaike info criterion	0.650876	
Sum squared resid	3.058588	Schwarz criterion	0.743391	
Log likelihood	-8.088571	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.681033	
F-statistic	32.87250	Durbin-Watson stat	1.859113	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000003			

Null Hypothesis: D(INCA) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.445037	0.1383
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.661661	
5% level	-2.960411	
10% level	-2.619160	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(INCA,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:59
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022
Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(INCA(-1))	-0.763635	0.312320	-2.445037	0.0208
C	-0.002531	0.020248	-0.124975	0.9014
R-squared	0.170912	Mean dependent var	-0.015169	
Adjusted R-squared	0.142323	S.D. dependent var	0.117698	
S.E. of regression	0.109001	Akaike info criterion	-1.532570	
Sum squared resid	0.344558	Schwarz criterion	-1.440055	
Log likelihood	25.75484	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.502412	
F-statistic	5.978206	Durbin-Watson stat	1.366742	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.020793			

Null Hypothesis: D(INCA,2) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.306586	0.0001
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.670170	
5% level	-2.963972	
10% level	-2.621007	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(INCA,3)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:59
 Sample (adjusted): 1993 2022
 Included observations: 30 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(INCA(-1),2)	-1.399919	0.263808	-5.306586	0.0000
C	-0.015842	0.021370	-0.741310	0.4647
R-squared	0.501423	Mean dependent var	-0.016076	
Adjusted R-squared	0.483617	S.D. dependent var	0.162881	
S.E. of regression	0.117046	Akaike info criterion	-1.388154	
Sum squared resid	0.383595	Schwarz criterion	-1.294741	
Log likelihood	22.82231	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.358271	
F-statistic	28.15985	Durbin-Watson stat	1.491050	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000012			

Null Hypothesis: D(GEXP) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.382265	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.661661	
5% level	-2.960411	
10% level	-2.619160	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(GEXP,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/02/25 Time: 01:00
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022
 Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GEXP(-1))	-1.168193	0.183037	-6.382265	0.0000
C	-0.097920	0.284656	-0.343993	0.7333
R-squared	0.584130	Mean dependent var	-0.001321	
Adjusted R-squared	0.569789	S.D. dependent var	2.412935	
S.E. of regression	1.582654	Akaike info criterion	3.818425	
Sum squared resid	72.63904	Schwarz criterion	3.910940	
Log likelihood	-57.18558	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.848582	
F-statistic	40.73330	Durbin-Watson stat	2.042121	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Null Hypothesis: GEXP has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.501041	0.5202
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.653730	
5% level	-2.957110	
10% level	-2.617434	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(GEXP)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/02/25 Time: 00:59
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2022
 Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GEXP(-1)	-0.152311	0.101470	-1.501041	0.1438
C	0.848596	0.674391	1.258313	0.2180
R-squared	0.069858	Mean dependent var	-0.079572	
Adjusted R-squared	0.038853	S.D. dependent var	1.553078	
S.E. of regression	1.522608	Akaike info criterion	3.739188	
Sum squared resid	69.55010	Schwarz criterion	3.830797	
Log likelihood	-57.82702	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.769554	
F-statistic	2.253124	Durbin-Watson stat	2.153882	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.143798			

Null Hypothesis: IND has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.917561	0.3204
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.653730	
5% level	-2.957110	
10% level	-2.617434	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(IND)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/02/25 Time: 01:00
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2022
 Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IND(-1)	-0.264404	0.137886	-1.917561	0.0647
C	1.297661	0.682726	1.900704	0.0670
R-squared	0.109185	Mean dependent var	-0.010343	
Adjusted R-squared	0.079492	S.D. dependent var	0.169832	
S.E. of regression	0.162942	Akaike info criterion	-0.730367	
Sum squared resid	0.796500	Schwarz criterion	-0.638778	
Log likelihood	13.68619	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.700021	
F-statistic	3.677040	Durbin-Watson stat	1.257180	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.064732			

Null Hypothesis: D(IND) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.014919	0.0445
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.661661	
5% level	-2.960411	
10% level	-2.619160	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(IND,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/02/25 Time: 01:00
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022
 Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IND(-1))	-0.784596	0.260238	-3.014919	0.0053
C	-0.015011	0.031211	-0.480948	0.6342
R-squared	0.238640	Mean dependent var		-0.023643
Adjusted R-squared	0.212386	S.D. dependent var		0.194983
S.E. of regression	0.173043	Akaike info criterion		-0.608213
Sum squared resid	0.868372	Schwarz criterion		-0.515698
Log likelihood	11.42730	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.578055
F-statistic	9.089740	Durbin-Watson stat		1.493277
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005298			

Appendix III: Co-integration Test Result

Date: 11/30/24 Time: 22:27
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022
 Included observations: 31 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend (restricted)
 Series: IND ELEC
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.514988	27.96588	25.87211	0.0271
At most 1	0.163513	5.534875	12.51798	0.5215

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level
 **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.514988	22.43100	19.38704	0.0175
At most 1	0.163513	5.534875	12.51798	0.5215

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level
 **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b'S11*b=I):

IND	ELEC	@TREND(91)
7.351383	-5.082244	0.222890
3.133335	1.558667	-0.072580

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(IND)	-0.007542	-0.067417
D(ELEC)	0.196840	-0.057705

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 17.87554

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

IND	ELEC	@TREND(91)
1.000000	-0.691332	0.030319
	(0.09233)	(0.00590)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(IND)	-0.055443
	(0.23610)
D(ELEC)	1.447049
	(0.33734)

Appendix IV: Vector Error Correction Model

Vector Error Correction Estimates

Date: 11/30/24 Time: 22:45

Sample (adjusted): 1992 2022

Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1	
IND(-1)	1.000000	
ELEC(-1)	-0.189031 (0.09239) [-2.04608]	
C	-3.435279	
Error Correction:	D(IND)	D(ELEC)
CointEq1	-0.360399 (0.20463) [-1.76125]	0.405487 (0.39222) [1.03384]
D(IND(-1))	0.438440 (0.28506) [1.53806]	0.241010 (0.54639) [0.44110]
D(ELEC(-1))	-0.034306 (0.10731) [-0.31970]	-0.196003 (0.20568) [-0.95297]
C	-0.015536 (0.03109) [-0.49967]	0.043032 (0.05959) [0.72207]
R-squared	0.127049	0.086712
Adj. R-squared	0.030054	-0.014764
Sum sq. resids	0.775955	2.850790
S.E. equation	0.169526	0.324938
F-statistic	1.309857	0.854504
Log likelihood	13.17145	-6.998034
Akaike AIC	-0.591706	0.709551
Schwarz SC	-0.406676	0.894581
Mean dependent	-0.012641	0.034661
S.D. dependent	0.172132	0.322566
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)	0.002266	
Determinant resid covariance	0.001719	
Log likelihood	10.69999	
Akaike information criterion	-0.045161	
Schwarz criterion	0.417416	
Number of coefficients	10	

Appendix V: Residual Tests

VEC Residual Heteroskedasticity Tests (Levels and Squares)

Date: 11/30/24 Time: 23:21

Sample: 1990 2022

Included observations: 31

Joint test:		
Chi-sq	df	Prob.
12.74748	18	0.8064

Individual components:

Dependent	R-squared	F(6,24)	Prob.	Chi-sq(6)	Prob.
res1*res1	0.028238	0.116233	0.9935	0.875369	0.9899
res2*res2	0.172400	0.833250	0.5562	5.344387	0.5005
res2*res1	0.017389	0.070787	0.9983	0.539057	0.9973

VEC Residual Portmanteau Tests for Autocorrelations

Null Hypothesis: No residual autocorrelations up to lag h

Date: 11/30/24 Time: 23:18

Sample: 1990 2022

Included observations: 31

Lags	Q-Stat	Prob.*	Adj Q-Stat	Prob.*	df
1	0.141589	---	0.146309	---	---
2	2.223647	0.8980	2.371957	0.8825	6
3	6.983997	0.7270	7.642344	0.6637	10

*Test is valid only for lags larger than the VAR lag order.
df is degrees of freedom for (approximate) chi-square distribution after adjustment for VEC estimation (Bruggemann, et al. 2005)

VEC Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests

Date: 11/30/24 Time: 23:19

Sample: 1990 2022

Included observations: 31

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lag h

Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.
1	1.823239	4	0.7682	0.454918	(4, 48.0)	0.7683
2	2.423348	4	0.6584	0.608393	(4, 48.0)	0.6585

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lags 1 to h

Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.
1	1.823239	4	0.7682	0.454918	(4, 48.0)	0.7683
2	7.238328	8	0.5112	0.915745	(8, 44.0)	0.5126

*Edgeworth expansion corrected likelihood ratio statistic.

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.009819	Prob. F(2,29)	0.9902
Obs*R-squared	0.021656	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9892
Scaled explained SS	0.057208	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9718

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID^2

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/02/24 Time: 19:16

Sample: 1991 2022

Included observations: 32

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.078229	0.037003	2.114121	0.0432
DINCA	0.024256	0.354622	0.068399	0.9459
DGEXP	-0.002781	0.024309	-0.114408	0.9097
R-squared	0.000677	Mean dependent var		0.078482
Adjusted R-squared	-0.068242	S.D. dependent var		0.202245
S.E. of regression	0.209032	Akaike info criterion		-0.203605
Sum squared resid	1.267131	Schwarz criterion		-0.066190
Log likelihood	6.257651	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.158055
F-statistic	0.009819	Durbin-Watson stat		1.087894
Prob(F-statistic)	0.990232			

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags

F-statistic	0.382562	Prob. F(2,27)	0.6858
Obs*R-squared	0.881824	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.6434

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/02/24 Time: 19:14

Sample: 1991 2022

Included observations: 32

Presample missing value lagged residuals set to zero.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DINCA	-0.035515	0.511846	-0.069387	0.9452
DGEXP	0.006414	0.036310	0.176641	0.8611
C	0.001138	0.053258	0.021372	0.9831
RESID(-1)	-0.153086	0.193624	-0.790637	0.4360
RESID(-2)	-0.099033	0.199235	-0.497068	0.6232
R-squared	0.027557	Mean dependent var		6.51E-18
Adjusted R-squared	-0.116509	S.D. dependent var		0.284630
S.E. of regression	0.300754	Akaike info criterion		0.577553
Sum squared resid	2.442230	Schwarz criterion		0.806574
Log likelihood	-4.240843	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.653467
F-statistic	0.191281	Durbin-Watson stat		2.017724
Prob(F-statistic)	0.940863			